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**Perspectives and Practices of Inclusivity in an Online Learning Environment:
An Ethnomethodological Study of an International School in Indonesia**

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Acceptance Page

This paper prepared by **ERDOLFO L. LARDIZABAL** with the title: “**Perspectives and Practices of Inclusivity in an Online Learning Environment: An Ethnomethodological Study of an International School in Indonesia**” is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Education, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the Master of Distance Education.

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Biographical Sketch

Erdolfo Lardizabal was born on 13 April 1965 in the Mountain Provinces, northern part of the Philippines. He finished as one among the top students in Don Bosco High and was a national scholar in completing his degree in Mechanical Engineering (BSME). He loves teaching, so that after graduation, he became an assistant instructor for Mathematics and Physics pending the result of his Board Examinations. After obtaining his license as a Mechanical Engineer (RME), he practiced his profession in the industry. Rising from the ranks, he became a Senior Manager and studying after work, he obtained his Law degree (LLB).

For the love of teaching, he accepted a job to handle all mathematics and all sciences in an Australian international school then later on joined his wife to be the curriculum coordinator in Gandhi School (Bali, Indonesia). In 2006, he and his wife were called to be school executives in one of the most prestigious international schools in Indonesia. He furthered his studies by completing his postgraduate degree in Physics (DST) and currently, after completing all units in his master's degree (MDE) he is now working on his requirements for graduation to obtain his fourth university degree.

The author is blessed by God with a loving wife, a principal in one of the sister schools where he is currently working, along with three children, and two grandchildren. For the author, everything that he accomplished and will achieve is all for the glory of God.

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The author offers this work to God and thank Him for his grace and mercy as without Him, the author is nothing.

He is thankful to his family, Mariza Agnes T. Lardizabal (wife), Joseph T. Lardizabal (son) and Hazel Acdol Lardizabal (daughter-in-law), Noelle Marie T. Lardizabal-Bandaay (Daughter) and Loysean Bandaay (son-in-law), Gabriel T. Lardizabal (son), Leone Bennett L. Bandaay (granddaughter), and Uriah Jade L. Bandaay (grandson), Emiaj Josh P. Torres (nephew), Cyrill Ann P. Torres (Niece), Jaime S. Torres (Brother-in-law) and Espie P. Torres (wife of brother-in-law) including relatives whose name may not have been written here but will not be forgotten as the author will always be grateful to all of them. The author's family has always been his inspiration and strength in completing insurmountable tasks given him.

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Dedication

The author of this ethnomethodological study of an international school on inclusion in an online learning environment would like to dedicate his work to students, teachers and administrators who believe that the “educational systems should not just cater to persons with disability but will cover learning needs of ‘all’ [emphasis on ‘all’] students in that institution (UNESCO, 1994) most specially in a Distance Education mode of learning.

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Abstract

To make an online learning environment inclusive, it is important that schools must value diversity so that teaching practices may be responsive to the academic needs of not just some but all students. Inclusion is not about the shortfall of an individual because of one's disability, disorder, or being gifted but it is how the school environment adjust to the individual. If so, then inclusion is of a social construct which entails an ethnomethodological approach in understanding inclusion. Instead of studying institutions that are committed and dedicated towards inclusive practices, this study zeroed in on an international school and inquired on practices that emerged from teachers' personal practical or sense making knowledge which has been developed overtime through their experiences. This study answered the following:

1. What teaching practices do western teachers in an international school aim to foster inclusivity in an online learning environment?
2. What is the perspective of the school on inclusivity that defines those practices?

To explore how teachers' actual ordinary and mundane discussion produce an answer as to how they (the teachers) make inclusion happen, this study analyzed the conversation of western international teachers on how they are making sense of policies brought forward by the school. The findings included ten (10) points that may guide schools on how to implement inclusion in an online learning environment. The contribution of this study to distance education includes the value of reflexive (sense-making) accountability of teachers. Such accountability contributed to the orderliness and shared performance to carry out inclusive education in an online learning environment.

Keywords: Online Learning; Inclusion; International Schools; Sense-Making Knowledge.

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Chapter I

RATIONALE OF THE STUDY

Inclusivity as a Practice or Non-Practice in Distance Education

Distance education is a form of teaching and learning in which there is a physical separation of teachers and students during instruction and various technologies are used to facilitate student-teacher, student-student, and student-content interactions. Distance education initially focused on nontraditional students, such as full-time workers, military personnel, and nonresidents or individuals in remote regions who are unable to attend brick-and-mortar classroom settings: however, distance education has become part of the educational world (Simonson & Berg, 2023). If inclusivity embraces the concept of not neglecting anyone, then addressing separation and reaching out to students who are remotely situated exhibit the very nature of distance education to be inclusive.

Instead of focusing on institutions which are very much devoted and committed into inclusive learning to understand inclusion in teaching and learning, in this case, the author opted to study an international school to understand how inclusion is practiced in an online or remote learning. Although the research data covered a spectrum of learning disabilities, the findings of the study pondered on the values in developing the full potential of all (emphasis on the word “all”) students with varied ‘learning’ capabilities. As part of its limitation, the study did not concentrate on ‘cultural’ diversity (because students in the subject international school are mostly locals and only twenty to twenty five percent are expatriates [the same ratio when it comes to western teachers who are working in the subject school]) or on a broader definition of inclusion to include gender equality but the study zeroed in on practices that may contribute to distance education. Such contribution comes in understanding the Perspectives and Practices of Inclusivity in an Online Learning Environment: An Ethnomethodological Study of an International School in Indonesia...2

practices and perspectives of how western teachers working in an international school make inclusion happen in their synchronous online teaching and learning which may not be found in the policies, but such practices may be developed based on the social construct of the western teachers' sense making mechanisms that may have been taken for granted by research but can be surfaced and highlighted by an ethnomethodological approach.

Inclusivity as a Research Focus

UNESCO made a breakthrough as regards special needs education by replacing it with inclusive education which means that all educational system will not just cater to persons with disability but will cover learning needs of all (emphasis on "all") students of that institution (UNESCO, 1994).

The International Baccalaureate (IB) along with all IB schools around the world supports the above principle. According to IB (2015),

"Inclusion is an ongoing process that aims to increase access and engagement in learning for all students by identifying and removing barriers. This can only be successfully achieved in a culture of collaboration, mutual respect, support, and problem solving. Inclusion is the learner profile in action, an outcome of dynamic learning communities."

In the same educational institution, regardless of their nationality or level of cognitive capability, all students can learn together. This means that teachers must put effort in removing impediments that could limit or curtail the participation and achievement of all learners. There is a need to ensure universal access to education, but this is no longer enough because there must be a guarantee for learners' active participation and achievement most specially for those that may be experiencing exclusion due to disability (IIEP/UNESCO, 2019).

Programmes in IB, such as those that BINUS SCHOOL Simprug, one among the IB Schools in Indonesia, has been running, for example, the Primary Years Programme (PYP) for Early Years to Grade 5, Middle Years Programme (MYP) for Grade 6 to Grade 10, and Diploma Programme (DP) for Grade 11 to Grade 12 - all aim to engage learning and allow access for 'all' students. Inclusive education or Inclusion refer to the concept of embracing the diversity of learners and all minority groups (IBO, 2015).

According to the Center for Applied Special Technology (CAST, 2020), to make Distance Education (DE) courses inclusive, it must follow flexibility on ways on how information is presented to students. Schools must allow ways on how students would demonstrate their knowledge and understanding. Finally, schools must find ways and means to engage students. If the school is inclusive, it is crucial to set up policies that value diversity to ensure practices that are responsive to the academic needs of all students. A study by Cook (Cook et.al, 2009) finds that while attitudes towards inclusive policies and disability protocols were strongly valued, they were not implemented properly.

If despite the idea that teachers value inclusion yet it has not been properly implemented according to Cook (2009), then it is crucial to know the thinking of teachers towards protocols: hence, the need to understand the teachers' sense making or personal practical knowledge which has been developed overtime through teachers' experiences when they were asked to review policies that relate to inclusion. Within the online learning environment, principles that reduce barriers to accessibility and inclusiveness are viewed not as a shortfall associated with the individual, but more as a social construct (Burgstahler & Cory, 2008).

If education as a practice is based upon organization, order, and structure (Elsay, 2021) then inclusion practices as part of teaching can be found in the same social sphere, that is in school classroom's regular tasks, activities, and lessons that create such an order.

Social order can be seen when the acts of human agents within that community is put at the centre of analysis (Have, 2002). In this study, the subject international school has almost half of its teachers to be expatriates and twenty three percent of them are western teachers. The concerned Diploma Programme (Grades 11 and 12) students are usually between 20% to 25% expatriates while all others are local students, children of economically privileged parents (BINUS SCHOOL Simprug, IBO Report, 2022). Since the study involves a school that is international, western expatriates as subject participants would best represent the study. International schools came about because diplomats who are working in a host country (other than their own) would rather have their children be educated in an educational system that is international in nature (Langford, 2005). The interaction of western schoolteachers can be examined to see how they are making sense about teaching strategies that are in place in an online learning atmosphere - by being critical to what was required and by discussing how learning barriers can be mitigated or removed to further improve inclusion practices.

The author's rationale is to study some inclusive practices and perspectives that may have been trivial but makes sense to educationists who made inclusion happen in an international school setting and to contextualize its contribution to wider field of distance education. If this is the case, then the issue is on how reflexivity (i.e., common-sense knowledge) found in school setting (for example, teacher's delivery of lesson and student responses) enabled western international teachers to

collaboratively achieve an improved procedure on how to handle and manage students that exhibit behaviour within the spectrum of hyperactiveness, impulsiveness and inattentiveness without neglecting all other students who do not fall in these behavioral spectra.

This situation of dealing with the above behaviour is complicated when teaching is in an online learning environment. Teachers are constrained in implementing inclusion due to lack of face-to-face interaction with students. It is challenging for teachers to ensure students' success. It is fair to say that online teachers cannot assess the students' individual needs and provide personalized support when they are not in the same room as their students.

If schools are to address diversity in the educational system, it is crucial to look at a wider range of studies with varied methodologies on how inclusion can be successfully implemented in an online learning setting. In this regard, there is a need to include those research that used ethnomethodological approach (which was considered here).

Most inclusive education investigation that came close to this ethnomethodological research were studies about schools catering only to those with severe disabilities instead of covering all students. It mentioned 'activities' that go with it in addressing learning difficulties of some students (Agustia, 2021). Other inclusion studies like Chan's (2015) research were about 'factors' that contribute to the success of inclusion practices in target international schools and issues that go with it. The study of Cash, Cox and Vaughn (2022) covered attitude of teachers in a distance education setting but was of quantitative research and not ethnomethodological in nature.

No study was made about how western international teachers disrupt a norm (in a form of policies), say challenging policies in their discussion during departmental meetings just to make sense of inclusion that is being practiced in school.

The knowledge derived in this ethnomethodological research provides insight on how teachers' practical reasoning contributes toward fostering inclusive online education in an international school setting.

Chapter II REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Inclusive Education in Traditional Context

According to Artiles (2011), the Scandinavian countries with the United States, England and Canada pioneered research in inclusive education. On the same literature, Artiles said that this was followed by other countries which likewise conducted studies and although inclusive education theory is the attention to multiple forms of differences, the bulk of the research focused on ability differences, i.e., students with disabilities (although the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization or UNESCO, in 1994 replaced this concept of inclusion of not just to catering to those who are disabled but rather considering 'all' students which was enshrined in what is known as the Salamanca Statement).

The paper of Nilholm (2014) talked so much about a massive amount of research put into to address inclusive education as an aftermath of the publication of the 1994 Salamanca Statement: however, there was a sense of lack of knowledge of how to actually create classrooms that were truly inclusive, the persistence of segregated educational practices and the diverse opinions among teachers about its appropriateness but limited its study to two schools in Sweden.

Floretta (2021) likewise talked about UNESCO's definition of inclusion where inclusive education means that all children – no matter who they are – can learn together in the same school. To address this definition, she rode on the research of Ron Mace (1970, US) who coined the term “Universal Design”. Floretta explained in her research the value of UDL or Universal Design for Learning, which was developed by CAST in 2011 (a non-profit education research and development organization that created the UDL Framework) to address the idea of inclusion for all and not just for the disabled. She borrowed the research of Alba Pastor (2012) in using his (Pastor's) analogy that if the only way for a person in a wheelchair to go up the theater is through a stair (an insurmountable barrier), it will be a universal design to build a ramp or a lift for that disabled person for him to have an access – and such access can be used by all. The term “Universal Design” was referring to “the design of products or physical environments which could be used by all without the need for further adaptation “(Alba Pastor, 2012).

The learners aged 3 - 19 come to school with their own ways of thinking as brought about by cultural and/or environmental upbringing as evidenced by their unique sets of experience, prior knowledge, and values. Schools have the responsibility to put in place processes to remove barriers such as but not limited to how schools are organized, its culture and policies and the schools' approaches to teaching and learning.

Floretta (2021) quoting on Meyer (2013) adapted the same concept to the educational environment where the approach was designed to ensure the development of motivation, skills, knowledge, and active participation of all individuals' learning process through multiple means of representation (various ways of acquiring information and knowledge), multiple means of expression (for demonstrating what

they know), and multiple means of engagement (to mirror learners' interests, challenge them appropriately and motivate them to learn) (Meyer et. Al. 2013).

UDL has actually been adopted by the International Baccalaureate Organization (IB) in its research and identified four principles of good practice to promote equal access to the curriculum for all learners: (a) affirming identity and building self-esteem, (b) valuing prior knowledge, (c) scaffolding and (d) extending learning. "Student learning is enhanced when these four principles of good practice are considered in conjunction with the IB approaches to teaching and learning, which are those deliberate strategies, skills and attitudes that permeate the teaching and learning environment" (IBO, 2019).

IB used the inclusion learning processes of multiple representation, expression and engagement by suggesting teaching strategies that involve Universal Design for Learning (UDL). When it comes to diagnostic categories (i.e., psychiatric diagnosis based upon observed and agreed behaviours) and learning challenges, IB is careful to emphasize that categorizing and labelling students do not provide sound indicators of a student's potential or application of appropriate teaching strategies (IBO, 2019).

Another way to address inclusive education is differentiating learning experiences which is something that usually educators do such as changing the classroom layout, scaffolding materials (breaking lessons into chunks) for struggling students or giving extra tasks for fast finishers (Floretta, 2021). Floretta's paper on UDL and differentiation have been well taken however, her research did not consider inclusive education of students who are into distance education specifically those who are working in an international school.

Most research were made to address some problems with inclusive education in international schools which were identified by Farrell (2000), for example (1) there

was a need to know how to create inclusivity in the classroom, (2) steps were identified to address the insistence of having separate educational practices for apparent disabled learners and (3) recognition of the perception of school community members on the propriety of inclusive practices. However, the findings was limited to diverse opinions among parents and teachers between expatriates and locals about the suitability of inclusive education (citing De Boer, Pijl, and Minnaert [2010, 2011] for reviews).

Agustian (20121) also came up with study on perspective of teachers on inclusion practices in an international setting but the author covered teachers view on admission of special education needs and those with severe disability. Agustian (2021) argued that in providing 'just' education for students, inclusion should be at the heart of endeavours, and this should not be distinguished in terms of cultural and ethnic backgrounds, socio-economic status, gender, religious beliefs and learning disabilities. This is in contrast to Kalantziz and Cope (2002) where the term 'inclusive education' is a matter of ongoing debate. The discussion was merely centered on the concept of placing students either in mainstream schools or special needs schools.

Chan (2015) on the other hand focused on the effectiveness of inclusive approaches and factors contributing to the success of inclusion in target international schools and noted the failure of teachers to commit to policies and procedure. Chan's end in mind was to find out the factors that contribute to the success of inclusion and knowing the degree of effectiveness of those factors start with an inquiry into practices that are operating in school. This type of framework of Chan (2015) seemed to be similar to all other researchers such as equity on five continents by Artiles (2011), inclusive education in the Middle East by Gaad (2010), complexity of inclusive education by Slee (2018), and inclusion practices by Agustian (2021). All studies

focused on inclusivity in international schools but not learners who are in distance education modality.

An example Framework used in other studies about inclusivity

Image 1: Research Framework of related studies (Chan, 2015).

Reading through these studies, up to now, there is a lack of knowledge in creating inclusive classrooms for 'all' learners (Göransson and Nilholm 2014): hence, the importance of addressing this gap by looking at further perspectives using other research tools such as that of ethnomethodology.

Attenborough (2012) provided an example of studying inclusive practices is understanding taken-for-granted behaviour of students through their conversation. Planning pedagogical inclusion intervention begins with a thorough knowing of students whom teachers are going to work with based on school information (Floretta, 2021). But there are data that may not be found in the school's information storage files. These may surface through conversation analysis. For example, exceptionally able students avoid positive assessments of their tasks which may be a barrier. This concept cannot be found in policies. For example, in a conversation analysis, Attenborough (2012) illustrated how students "not only do they routinely avoid positive

assessments of their tasks, but they also distance themselves from appearing ‘too clever’, having knowledge, or having worked hard. Above-average achievement and knowledge displays are disclaimed or accounted for, if not by students themselves” (Attenborough, 2021).

Extract 2: ES/JM-1: ‘Students watching television’ (Attenborough, 2012)

- 1 H: ↑O:h Lola : :. ↑Lola’s givin’ me some lo:ve.
2 (0.4)
3 S: (Probably cos we’re) £()£.
4 (0.7)
5 C: Heh >heh heh< [heh heh heh
6 S: [£ () £
7 (0.5)
8 H: She says mate ‘ve you done the readings for tomorrow’s
9 tutorial they’re bollocks. £h£
10 S: .Hheh

Moving forward, not knowing the students’ capability becomes an issue. As a matter of inclusion practice it is important to thoroughly understand exceptionally capable students of the above behaviour (or for other behaviours as well). This way, pedagogical intervention or student support may be provided for using Diagnostic Assessment (DA). This DA is a tool to accurately know students’ inclusion needs.

The Diagnostic Assessment (DA) also provides information on the demographic composition which may have an impact on learning and students’ interest. This DA may provide related inclusion strategies to deal with students having “difficulty of regulating their behaviour, regulating their motor skills, controlling their attention span, expressing their ideas among others. These may occur at different times during the

school career and may present individually or overlapped” (British Dyslexia Association, 2018 as quoted by Floretta, 2021). Attenborough did come up with a study of inclusive education but not in an online setting.

Inclusive Education in Distance Learning

At the time when the pandemic had taken hold in all parts of the world, studies emerged about inclusion in an online learning environment. For example, those undertaken by the Teaching and Learning Research Community (TLRC), a group of practitioners, scholars, and vendor representatives in online learning that met as part of the Digital Learning Annual Conference (DLAC) in Austin, Texas in February 2020 (Ortiz et. al, 2020). There was a rapid worldwide shift to emergency remote teaching.

Ortiz et. al (2020), citing Kozleski (2020) said that inclusion has been difficult in an online setting as it (inclusion) has been largely conceptualized as sharing physical space (the classroom) with other students. Kozleski’s idea is that in an online setting, inclusion should instead focus on meaningful beneficial interactions. Teaching in an online setting has been considered work of so-called miracle workers, rather than an intentional practice. Ortiz et. al (2020) finds that “inclusive education was always much more than sharing in-person space; moreover, in the present and in the future, what it means to share in-person space has changed radically. Instead, we have to focus on inclusion as a community-building effort.” The research, although was of a social construct of inclusive education practitioners whose sense making thinking would contribute to that community-building effort in addressing the needs of students in an online setting (Cash et. al, 2021), it merely touched but elaborate on the social order.

Burgstahler (2004) finds that distance education modality becomes a barrier to students who are experiencing learning difficulties if content is not formatted in an

accessible manner. Ann Dell et. al (2015) said that UDL principles have to be done proactively while considering impediments of learning while students are in an online learning. Quoting on Seale (2014): “Universal Design (UD) views incidence of learning difficulties not as a shortfall associated with the individual, but more as a social construct and therefore aids in decreasing barriers when the design of the product or environment is considered to begin with rather than waiting to remove barriers as they occur through individualized accommodations.” On the other hand, Hayden (2006) says that there is no line to debate upon in placement cases if parents can afford the tuition fees or if learning assessments should be adjusted to cater for those with severe disability so that their child can be in that international school. “This is mainly because international education as a concept is often argued to be inclusive in at least the sense of catering for children of many different national, cultural and linguistic backgrounds” (Hayden, 2006; Tange and Kastberg, 2013), but for those who experienced international schooling, as a form of international education, this may not always be the case because of the lack of knowledge in creating inclusive classrooms for all learners as mentioned by Göransson and Nilholm (2014). The same lack of knowledge about UDL was impeding the implementation of inclusion in an online learning environment according to the study of Cash et. al. (2020) where further study about teachers’ insight was part of its recommendation: hence, there is an interest in knowing various points of view among educationist who are practicing inclusive education (Bradley, 2016) as they (the teachers) are the ones implementing it in their day-to-day activities. Both Burgstahler (2004) and Hayden (2006) were of quantitative research rather than one of ethnomethodology.

Why are the above other studies limited?

The studies above are more into knowing why Inclusion works in some circumstances and it becomes challenging in other cases: however, there is no study about teachers' thoughts on policies imposed on them to understand their natural perspectives and how such inclusive practices makes sense to them as they commit to improving the practice.

In the study of Cash et. al (2020), it highlighted the perspectives and behaviour of teachers in implementing inclusion based on UDL where the finding was that teachers value policies and inclusive protocols in an online learning environment but were not properly implementing it. The study says that faculty placed little value towards providing accommodations to students with learning difficulties despite the inclusion policies in place. It did not go any further as regards the sense making thinking of faculty members which would have been interesting to know why inclusion works for some and not for others.

Another example is that of Chan's (2015) findings. It suggests that schools have been successful in raising teachers' awareness about inclusive education and creating a culture of accepting diversity but commitment of teachers towards this end varies. There was no study as to what was going on in the mind of practitioners when asked to commit although practices were identified but not on how the practice came about within the social sphere.

What warrants an ethnomethodological study?

Teachers' role in making their class inclusive seemed to be very crucial as they are the actors in inclusive education (Agustian, 2021). It is argued that teachers have mechanism in their everyday life on how to make sense of the practices they

developed but are actually taken for granted: hence, there is a need to do an ethnomethodological study to examine the teachers' sense making of their teaching practices in order to understand their perspective in accomplishing inclusive education in school. This sense-making mechanism (which was not considered by many researchers) is needed in getting further perspectives to address the lack of knowledge and commitment of teachers as they implement inclusion in an online learning environment.

Chapter III **RESEARCH FRAMEWORK AND RESEARCH QUESTIONS**

Ethnomethodology as an Approach

A theory, in general answers the 'why' questions. Ethnomethodology answers the 'how' questions specifically when people accomplish everyday life (Gubrium and Holstein, 2000). Ethnomethodology seeks to understand the skillful accomplishment of social reality through an unwavering commitment to studying the routines of everyday life (Have citing Prasad, 2005).

In the article by Sheffield (2017), he made mention that ethnomethodology was brought forward by Harold Garfinkel in the 1960s along with symbolic interactionist work of Erving Goffman and phenomenological description of Alfred Schutz. Blackstone (2016) proposed that social activities are enacted through conversation and how people interpret, maintains, and prolong their realities. Quoting on Blackstone, he said "clearly then, social reality here is viewed as having fixed and immutable but potentially in a state of construction and reconstruction."

According to Sheffield (2017), ethnomethodology pays attention to the accounts people produce together, how the accounts are received, and the context

within which the accounts are being provided. There are two distinct strands of ethnomethodology, i.e., linguistic, and situational. The former, now distinguished as conversational analysis, focuses on how conversations are structured, use indexical (i.e., talk and action) expressions and are often peppered with 'taken for granted' meanings. The latter requires people to cast their view over wider range of social activity and seek to understand the ways in which people negotiate the social contexts in which they find themselves (Cohen et. al, 2000). What was considered in the study is more of the former as the talk is taken in the widest sense aside from other forms of symbolic forms like facial expressions, gestures, pauses and uh hums. Ethnomethodology is more interested in the scene and the processes through which the group operates such as the 'exchanges' (discussion) of the participants in this study as they review inclusion policies and see how it is adapted in an online learning environment.

The study here was framed within the premise that there was a need to know the perspectives of western teachers (who are working as international educationists in Indonesia) about policies as they were asked to implement inclusion in school in an online learning environment. To find out the teachers' common-sense reasoning in committing to support inclusive education, the study must look at various documents, for example inclusion policies that the school may have collaboratively worked on and the transcripts of the western schoolteachers' discussion on the practical application of said policies so that they may effectively implement inclusion in school. The collected data were subjected to conversation analysis.

Image 2: Research Framework of related to this study (Lardizabal, 2023).

Research Questions

In 1994, UNESCO issued the Salamanca Statement (UNESCO, 1994). It says that inclusive education will be considered as a matter of policy across all international schools, that is, segregated educational solutions were to be avoided and mainstream classroom should open-up to diversity (Vislie, 2003).

International schools share the characteristic of fee-paying diplomat schools that usually admit students whose parents are called upon to work in many different countries (Langford, 2005). Increasingly, these international schools admit host country nationals as students. Its main selling point is more opportunities to learn through the medium of English, usually with native English Speakers recruited as teachers (Bunnell, 2019).

The International Baccalaureate (IB), which has been providing international curriculum since 1968, released its publication on inclusive education where it supports the call of the United Nations to make inclusive education as a matter of human right. IB claims that teaching in all IB schools is inclusive and values diversity (IBO, 2016).

Attitude towards student diversity policies and disability protocols were strongly valued by teachers: however, online learning environment is constraining for teachers in implementing inclusion because of the lack of face-to-face interaction with students (Cash et.al., 2022). If educational institutions are to be successful in addressing this learning barrier, it is crucial to look at studies of varied methodologies on how inclusion can be successfully implemented in an online learning setting including that of an ethnomethodological approach.

Many studies have been conducted on inclusivity such as examining equity on five continents by Artiles (2011), inclusive education in the Middle East by Gaad (2010), complexity of inclusive education by Slee (2018), and inclusion practices by Agustian (2021). However, ethnomethodological inclusive education studies seemed to be rare as findings may arguably be trivial (Craig) although Elsey (2021) provided one ethnomethodological study about adults with learning difficulties. Unfortunately, it was limited only to one instance where a student challenged the teacher's authority, and the responses of the latter became the focus of the investigation to arrive at inclusive practices. It did not elaborate on important teachers' points of view.

This study considered inclusive education to be predicated upon structure, which order can be found in the classroom within activities, lessons, and assessments (Elsey, 2021) when virtually conducted. These developed teaching practices based on teachers' internal discussion are collaborative achievements for the school as it becomes a source on how to improve teaching strategies.

The pivotal issue is how various sense-making concept enabled teachers to fill-in the gaps in the shortcoming of established norms (policies) to make the teaching practices become more practically inclusive in their day-to-day virtual class activities.

There is a need to know how western teachers who are working in an international school in Indonesia make sense of school policies to understand their perspectives in implementing inclusion in a distance education modality. Looking at the above context, this study aims to answer the following questions:

1. What teaching practices do western teachers in an international school aim to foster inclusivity in an online learning environment?
2. What is the perspective of the school on inclusivity that defines those practices?

Chapter III METHODOLOGY

Research Design

Conversation Analysis (CA) was used in this qualitative research to look at the naturally occurring conversation of western educators who are working as international teachers in an IB School in Indonesia.

By referring to the social theory and methods of CA, valuable perspectives (into ways in which inclusion practices are enacted and negotiated in online learning environments) provided rich understanding of inquiries set forth in this research. Ethnomethodology is a form of social theory that looks at how social order is made possible by examining the interaction of human participants. Data from this social interaction was studied to gain insights into the practices and processes (Have, 2002).

The work here used a qualitative approach where its design was limited to a conversation among western English teachers in an international school in Indonesia. The coverage was a discussion in one of their meetings about inclusion policies that were asked of them to implement. The focus of the study is to understand their common-sense knowledge on how to make inclusion work by analyzing practices that

is meaningful to them but may have been overlooked either by research or simply by the protocols that the teachers have had in school. Ethnomethodology is concerned more with how the teachers accomplish their everyday life (Gubrium, 2000) by reasoning, conversation, and interaction among themselves. This qualitative study which relates to sense-making lies in a social world of accommodating multiple realities: hence, the findings here would be unique and distinct because different observers may see the world in different ways (Vom Lehn, 2014). Because of possible variations, further studies may be taken.

Also, in answering the second research question as regards perspective of the school based on documents, from an ethnomethodological point of view, documents are seen as indexical (objects that have meaning in context) and can be inferred from to understand how practices were constituted (Hak, 1992).

Research Locale

The sequences here were taken from an audio-visual recording of an English Department meeting in BINUS SCHOOL Simprug (BSS), located in Jakarta, Indonesia. The school went into full synchronous online learning and at the time of this study the school was trying to do a hybrid, i.e., students attend school on a face-to-face mode while half of the class will join virtually from home. However, because of another surge of Covid cases, the school went back into synchronous online learning. It was in this situation when the school was visited by the International Baccalaureate Organization (IBO) representatives for its regular authorization which has been conducted every five years. As part of the IBO authorization processes, the school (referring to BSS) was required to review its old inclusion policy: hence, the meeting among DP Teachers per department. This entailed the English Department

comprising of western international teachers to meet online (the Covid-19 Pandemic made it difficult for teachers to meet on a face-to-face setting) using the Microsoft Teams (MsTeams) audio-visual platform. The meeting was recorded, and such audio-visual recording was submitted to the school's Diploma Programme Coordinator (DPC) for review which the latter re-transcribed and important points were summarized. The updated transcription was the one used for this study. It is worth noting that the interaction of western teachers was more critical than others since all of them are Critical Thinking (Theory of Knowledge, TOK) Teachers. In TOK, teachers teach IB students to look at all perspectives including counterarguments, dissenting opinion or opposing views as these are considered healthy when it comes to evaluating ideas. Therefore, it was not a surprise when IB Teachers here challenged the existing norm in their discussion.

SITE ACCESS (CONSENT, ETC.)

An overview of the participants involved in the interaction are as follows:

JM – [REDACTED]; Nationality – Canadian; Head of the DP English Department; He is also teaching (1) English A: Language and Literature, (2) Theory of knowledge, and (3) Psychology.

SG – [REDACTED]; Nationality - British; He is teaching (1) English A: Language and Literature, (2) English B, and (3) Theory of knowledge.

NY – [REDACTED]; Nationality – British; He is teaching (1) English A: Language and Literature and (2) Theory of knowledge.

JM called NY and SG to join the online MsTeams Chat at 13:27h WIB (Jakarta Time), i.e., 06:27h UTC. Unfortunately, he turned off the transcription (see image 3 below). This was the reason why the DPC had to replay the video and re-run the

automatic transcription separately but had to review and edit it to conform with what was being discussed in the audio-visual recording.

Image 3. Participants involved in the discussion (NY, SG and JM)

After the transcription was made, the author asked the participants if he can use it for this study and the consent was given by all. This consent was noted by the school principal (see image 4).

Image 4: Copy of consent given by JM, SG and NY to use their transcribed discussion to be analysed and used for this study. This consent was also noted by the school's Principal.

Research Instruments

Ethnomethodology focuses on the study of methods that individuals use in “doing” social life to produce mutually recognizable interactions within a situated context, producing orderliness. It explores how members' actual, ordinary activities produce and manage settings of organized everyday situations (Pillay, 2019).

Data Collection Procedure

Data were transcribed using the basic Jefferson Transcription System (2004). The source came from the conversation of three International Baccalaureate (IB) Diploma Programme (DP) Teachers who were teaching in BINUS SCHOOL Simprug in Jakarta, Indonesia. Members are westerners (i.e., they came from Canada [JM] and United Kingdom [both SG and NY]) reiterating the above information.

As a disclosure, since the study is about inclusion practices, the extracts of the sequences did not go to the extent of identifying the Turn Construction Units (TCUs) and corresponding functions but in some parts of the extracts, it indicated the Transition Relevance Places (TRPs) according to the Jefferson Transcription System (2004). This way, the more important practices based on sense-making mechanisms of teachers were identified.

In context, the school at that time was completing the important documents for an IB Evaluation to extend its authorization to use the IB as the school's curriculum. One among the requirements of IB was to complete the school's Inclusion Policy and corresponding school's Program Development Plan (PDP) on Inclusion. These documents (see Appendix 6) were submitted to the International Baccalaureate (IB) Team of Evaluators who were at that time scheduled to visit and assess the school's implementation of IB's Standards and Practices in May 2022.

Data Collection and Analysis

A. Conversation in Appendix 1: Focusing on Behaviour and Not To Categorize

In Appendix 1 extracting lines (L) 001 to 007, JM provided the context of their meeting. L001 and L003 were referring to the meeting being recorded, and the computer-generated transcription being turned off by JM. The proceeding was video

recorded using Microsoft Teams (MsTeams) “meet” feature (The meeting was still online although slowly, the school is moving towards face-to-face discussion rather than virtual sessions). JM, who was the controller of virtual meeting, turned off the ‘transcription’ feature (which was unfortunate as the study needs the transcribed discussion): however, to get back the transcription, the video was replayed in a separate MsTeams “meet” feature to capture the computer-generated conversation discussion into text-type. This very raw transcription was reviewed by the school’s DP Coordinator and annotated it using the basic Jefferson Transcription System (2004) as mentioned above. All four parts of the conversation were placed in the appendices 1 – 4 in this paper for reference. For purposes of analysis, extracts in terms of lines were reiterated here, to wit:

Extracted Lines 001 – 007 (Re: Context of the Meeting)

001 JM: We are now being recorded. Yeah. I turned off the transcription
002 SG: ok
003 JM: I know (.) stop transcription
004 Ok (.) let's begin (.) so last week we ::
005 I mean we looked at behaviours (.) I guess a (.)
006 umm (.) associated with autism
007 in a more general kind of way (.) Today we're doing basically it's (.) the
same activity
008 we're looking at behaviour associated with ADHD ADD. But
009 we're in no way diagnosing our students (.) you know, we're just
010 looking at the behaviours and then possible things that we can
011 do or you know (.) looking at challenges that might arise and
012 then possible ways that we can deal with those challenges.

013 Again:: NOT (.) not diagnosing.

((SG and NY were listening as shown on screen))

014 So I (.) I don't know if there's any need to go into ADHD and
ADD in

015 the difference and all of that.

((Transition Relevance Place, or TRP here))

In L008 and L013, JM implied that the group should not be diagnosing (L013) because DP Teachers are not specialist (IBO, 2019) but instead the group needs to focus only on behaviours that they can observe in their online class. L006 made mention of autism. Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) is a developmental disability by differences in brain, for example, differences in the size and shape of say amygdala and the prefrontal cortex, which are involved in social and emotional processing (Schuetze & Park, 2019). JM noted that teaching strategies for this spectrum were discussed in their last meeting and that whatever procedure they have had last time in dissecting the policy on how to deal with autism, the same procedure will be taken up for their next inclusion case discussion which is part of their meeting's agenda (see L007).

JM bypassed the procedure of referring to the IB Document "Meeting Student Diversity in the Classroom: Removing Barriers to Learning" (IBO, 2019) and instead instructed SG and NY to focus on behaviour and not in diagnosing students (L014). JM's routine knowledge of previous procedure (see L008-L015) offered him to disregard any reference to the IB document and immediately had an activity that is dependent on the common-sense constructs and categories, with 'routine knowledge' offering the individuals with effective responses to recurrent situations (Rogers, 1983).

Teachers in IB schools were issued with Learning Diversity and Inclusion guide which was republished in 2018 where it stated the following: “learner variability upholds that categorizing student according to diagnostic labels (ADHD, Dyslexia, and so on) does not provide sound indications of student’s potential or appropriate teaching strategies (IBO, 2018). This reinforces the call of JM not to ‘label’ students as a condition when reviewing inclusive practices specially when students are on home learning program or HLP.

B. Conversation Covered in Appendix 2: Inclusion Strategies on Hyperactive Behaviour

In Appendix 2, extract L034 - L044, a similar concept of Rogers (1983) on authentic conversation is shown with the interaction of SG and JM. The latter called the attention of the former to share his (SG’s) thoughts about hyperactivity (a picture was shown on a slide that was being shared by JM on screen with SG and NY) which is a behaviour that the school’s inclusion policy should have been addressing by teachers in school. Based on the conversation, JM was showing an illustration of a student being hyperactive who is about to tumble with the student leaning backwards and reaching the floor with both hands with feet are on the floor while his classmates are having a class activity. SG reacted by saying that hyperactivity doesn’t have to be the same as what was shown on screen. SG dissented to what was given as an example of hyperactivity (see L037-039) as there are other ways to represent such a behaviour. The conversation was as follows, to wit:

Extracted Lines 034 – 044 (Clarifying Various Representation of Hyperactivity)

034 JM: So maybe Sam, we can start with you : : issues with hyperactivity (.)

035 Now if (.) if there are other things that you do, please (.) please
let
036 us know.
037 SG: So just before I (.) I before I start talking about the teaching
038 strategies, the : : just a comment on the representation of
039 hyperactivity, the (.) the cartoon kid is obviously doing hands
downs
040 and so on.
041 Umm.
042 It doesn't have to be so obvious, right? There are lots
043 of different ways a person can be hyperactive, but not be
044 cartoonishly so/

SG's dissent reveals that simple identification does not provide sufficient information regarding the specific manifestation of the individual (Elsay, 2021) - in this case the student doing a stunt to represent hyperactivity. At this point in time, SG was being critical on what is being presented to him. For example, online learning can be boring, and students find no motivation to make it through a class: hence, they find themselves fidgety (Gutte,2023). In an article by James McGough (2020), there are ways for students who are hyperactive to release their energy by incorporating various movement breaks or activities which allows online students to move around refocuses the task at hand: hence, these various ways would better represent hyperactiveness.

After clarifying that hyperactivity can be represented in various ways, SG (in the subsequent conversation) provided his idea on how to handle hyperactivity. In Appendix 2, extract L048 – L050, SG was reflecting on empowering student whether explicitly or impliedly. SG somehow reacted to student being labelled hence need for

the case to be dealt with because of his being hyperactive (L054: ... somebody being structured because of hyperactivity).

Extracted Lines 048 – 063 (Perspectives of Teachers on Hyperactivity, Part 1)

048 SG: The things which I will be drawn to here would be : : <explicitly>
049 teaching modes of behaviour (.) because I like the idea of
050 empowering a student to recognize what's affecting them.
051 [umm
052 JM: [I'm sorry, is it this explicitly I need to
053 SG: [Yeah. Yeah, not necessarily.
054 <It immediately in reaction to somebody being structured because of
hyperactivity,
055 but just, um (.)
056 generally incorporating that into your, um (.) um teaching
method.
057 Umm (.)
058 And (.)
059 I can see you for younger kids.
060 Uh. Using excess energy in a positive way might be : : might be
061 more valuable than for our kids.
062 [Uh : :
063 JM: yeah.

((Transition Relevance Place, TRP, here))

SG was looking at ways to use that energy of the hyperactive student in a positive way because the child will value it (L060 – L061) but at this point, SG seemed to be unsure how. In order to value students, schools have to let students need to feel

comfortable and engaged in the learning process by allowing teachers to make a classroom environment that treat all students with respect and kindness, celebrating diversity and acknowledging each student's unique strengths and abilities (Bucholz, 2009).

In Appendix 2, extract L064 – 089 showed conversation between SG and JM and the former's concern on the inclusion strategy of 'time-out corner' in dealing with hyperactivity.

Extracted Lines 064 – 067 (Appendix 2 Idea of "Time Out": Hyperactive, Part 2)

064 SG: And then the : :

065 A comment on the timeout facility in my previous school↑

066 one of our students did need a place to go and just vent.

067 Well, I didn't see it being that helpful to him in particular. So

Jumping to L107 – L109, the same sentiment was raised by NY who finds time-out time to be isolatory: hence, implied to be punitive for the hyperactive learner.

107 NY: = Uh, and it helps them. So, I'm hopeful that I don't think the

108 timeout corner works. I don't think it's affected it's

109 isolatory (.) [It's =

((NY finds the school's idea of time-out likewise to be not useful as it is isolatory))

In the discussion about inclusion procedure of hyperactive student being placed in a timeout corner, SG considered it as a place where a student may express his say unexpressed venting: however, NY challenged it as it is keeping the student in isolation: hence, punitive. Looking at another perspective, in an article authored by Tracy Mercier (28 July 2014), a Responsive Classroom consultant, she claims that Time-out is positive, supportive and respectful strategy used to help a student who is

beginning to lose self-control to regain it so that they can do their best in learning. However, in an online setting, a timeout will be difficult to implement because there is no authority (at home) to support unless the parents are willing to do the role. Following the conversation, NY still noted this procedure to be in question. SG finds it helpful based on his experience in his other school while NY finds it reclusive (although SG eventually agreed).

And going back to the conversation in L099 – L106, NY was actually suggesting the use of “spinners” based on his experience as it does provide hyperactive students some focus into what they are doing which SG and JM agreed.

Extracted Lines 099 – L106 (Use of Spinner: Hyperactivity, Part 3)

- 099 NY: = it's not distracting me. They've got one
100 of those spinners (.) I see you've [got one =
101 SG: [Yeah.
102 NY: = Questions through
103 do (.) do something. Is very creative output.
104 And I do all the time.
105 It helps me focus my [ideas =
106 JM: [yeah.

According to research by Hartanto et. al (2016) there is an increased attention and alertness when children and adults fidget. It is an outlet of energy to distract the hand. Fidgeting toys or activities may improve a person with hyperactive behaviour to be able to pay attention, recall information and solve problems (Hartanto, 2016). As a matter of fact, IB specified doodling, drawing, or playing with stress ball in its publication (IBO, 2019). These ways actually force one's brain to increase its effort to focus on the task at hand (Hartanto, 2016). But then, there is little research that says

spinners are effective in this effect (Calfas, 2017). Nonetheless it is noted that based on his experience, NY finds spinners to work for him to focus on ideas which JM agreed.

In conversation lines 117 – 119, NY continued to share his own way of finding time to sit down with the hyperactive students to help them focus. One thing more that he noticed is that this inclusive strategy cannot be found in the list – referring to the document that JM was showing.

Extracted Lines 117 – L119 (Sitting down with hyperactive Learner: Hyperactivity, Part 4)

117 NY: No (.) side (.) do I (.) I sit down with them.

118 Hyperactivity. And I tried to help them focus on it. It's (.) it's (.)

119 not on this list, strangely.

Although JM agreed citing his own experience (L075 – 084) but prior to this, JM provided a good alternative of having a time-out area in the counselor's office (which is not punitive) so as to comply with the suggested Inclusion strategy of time-out to address the hyperactive behaviour of students in class (L071 – 073).

Extracted Lines 071 – 073 (Back to Time-Out but with Counselor: Hyperactivity, Part 5)

071 JM: [But and one is OCD actually and (.) and he knew that he had,
he

072 could go to the guidance counselor's office for his

073 timeout.

((JM provided an alternative of going to counselor's office as place for time-out))

SG finds the idea of time-out time area, such as the counselor's office (or say the toilet) than a time-out corner as providing option on where to go will help the student to develop coping mechanism that is healthy and helpful for the student can carry out until his adult life (L087 – L088).

Extracted Lines 086 – 089 (Time-Out Provides Students to Cope Up: Hyperactivity, Part 6)

086 SG: Well, that (.) and that's the (.) that's the important thing that we're

087 talking about in general, is providing students with coping

088 mechanisms that will be healthy and helpful that they can carry

089 into their adult lives.

The above agreed idea of time-out corner as inclusive strategy as being isolatory and punitive for hyperactive students - including the suggested use of spinners and sending the hyperactive student to the Counseling Office were not found in the policy. In this ethnomethodological study, these ideas are both social and shared methods due to common-sense reasoning (Rawls, 2008).

After dealing with hyperactivity, the group closed it and went on to the next case which is about impulsive behaviour and the inclusion strategies of Peer Support, Safety Rules, and class taking a break if impulsiveness becomes uncontrolled (see Appendix 3 L158 – L315)

C. Conversation Covered in Appendix 3: Inclusion Strategies on Impulsive Behaviour

The conversation about inclusion strategies to address impulsive behaviour started with “safety” (L158 – L166) as impulsive students have the tendency to be unaware of any danger or if they are, they have the difficulty of controlling their action as impulsiveness may be considered to be neurobiological in nature (IBO, 2019). NY’s comments in L164 (... imagine sciences...) were referring to cases in the Sciences as it is here where there are a lot of delicate safety rules which could be breached (and may cause harm) by an impulsive student.

Extracted Lines 158 – 166 (Danger in the Science Laboratory: Impulsiveness, Part 1)

158 JM: OK, next one.

((next one refers to JM presenting his next slide which is about impulsive behaviour))

159 [Cancel this.

160 SG: [Y::es (0.8)

161 NY: Umm, ignoring danger (.) you've been very loose.

162 I don't (o.8)

163 Reminds me up earlier. Umm, well it this morning. Danger or not,

164 I'm not sure it's extended. I'm sure it works. You imagine science

165 And then what?

166 JM: Umm

In relation to students who may not be aware of danger due to impulsive behaviour, one inclusion practice that NY introduced was the “use of a timer” (L170). The rationale behind the use of timer was NY’s concept that teacher must remind

students of their place as students (L168) and this needs to be done politely (L169). Analyzing, this makes sense to NY as for him, use of the timer is reasonably a tool to remind people which system when used does not offend people most specially the sensitive impulsive students. Again, this concept is based on NY's day-to-day experience but not found in the inclusion policy or in the IB Document.

Extracted Lines 167 – 170 (Use of Timer: Impulsiveness, Part 2)

- 167 NY: but somewhere to interrupt this and what's out of town. And
168 I just have to remind them of their place. But in a very
169 polite and like manner.
170 Using a timer, [I was like

The use of timer being effective for impulsive behaviour of students in any learning environment whether online or offline is corroborated by research such as that of Bennett (2018) where it talked about the idea that “timers can serve as an excellent reminder to focus on [the dangers that surrounds the completion of] the task at hand (Bennett, 2018).

Another practice is being explicit when discussing safety that may be a concern for impulsive behaviour of a student. In the conversation between SG and NY, the former in L254 in a way expressed the importance of explicit discussion on safety where latter added to the idea that breaking safety rules have its own repercussion (see L259: transgressed boundary is going to be serious ramifications) where JM agreed.

Extracted Lines 253 – 261 (Safety Again: Impulsiveness, Part 3)

- 253 SG: Not that ((pointing to upper line of the slide))
254 Yeah, explicit discussion of safety is (.) never gonna go on

((back to safety, SG believes that this must be explicitly discussed apparently in class))

255 this. Right.

256 NY: Well, I was just gonna mention that because with (.)

257 outwards (.) Andrew discusses some pretty big news
challenging. So

258 we can see a EX boundaries and it's just as simple as a dude

259 transgressed boundary is going to be serious ramifications for

((NY followed up explicit safety rules that if not followed, there are serious consequences))

260 [them.

261 JM: [And it's. Yeah.

However, analyzing the conversation in L264 – 268, JM's experience with Oliver (L267 was an inference of Oliver being one of the apparent impulsive students) has an element of students challenging rules. The statement in L265 where JM said, "I don't want this to turn into like, God exist! and the student saying back 'no he doesn't!'" is an analogy of JM using religion, where Oliver has the tendency to challenge whatever the teacher is saying. JM's common-sense knowledge provides that perspective as explained by Cicourel (1995) on stock knowledge of professionals to identify possible situation where despite explicit discussion of rules, impulsive students may not follow it where safety may be compromised. The conversation in L259 above of showing consequences to action, according to NY, may help in addressing this concern.

Extracted Lines 264 – 268 (Respecting Students' Point of View: Impulsiveness, Part

4)

264 JM: Respect.

265 I don't want to turn this into like (.) God exists. No, he doesn't!

266 Yes, he does. Well,

267 NY: but you're referring to Oliver

268 JM: Yeah (h)

((JM raised the issue that students may question the rules; used analogy to religion))

((Transition Relevance Place, TRP, here))

Being explicit on rules would address impulsive behaviour in an online setting as expectations are clear and consequences outlined which may mitigate in breaching such rules as implied in the above conversation among the participants.

The group went on to note teachers' attitude of being sarcastic (see L212 – 214). Here, NY admitted that he may have run out of patience on students when impulsiveness was being discussed: hence, the use of sarcasm. It is evident that correcting this teacher's attitude of using sarcasm on students especially impulsive ones can also be part of inclusion strategies in an online learning environment.

Corroborating evidence was presented by Colston (1997) which was quoted by Pickering (2018). According to the study, the negative emotional impact of a message is enhanced, rather than muted, using sarcasm.

Extracted Lines 253 – 261 (Removing Teacher's Sarcasm: Impulsiveness, Part 5)

212 NY: I think E is the most. [Don't have patient =

((N was referring to item E in the slide shown by JM about 'not using sarcasm'))

213 JM: [yeah.

214 And yeah, it's sarcastic

((Transition Relevance Place, TRP, here))

In the conversation about "peer support" as an inclusion strategy (L215) as raised by NY, SG finds this to have a negative implication. His argument in L219 and L 222 is that teachers are putting a lot of responsibility on the shoulders of the peer in dealing with a student having impulsive behaviour. For SG this is not a good idea. NY agreed (L221).

Extracted Lines 215 – 222 (Unnecessary Pressure on Peers: Impulsiveness, Part 6)

215 NY: = support works using groups

((N was referring to the strategy item D which is 'arranging for peer support'))

216 JM: yeah.

217 SG: One thing I'll point out about using peer support and the

218 video (.) it's suggested seating the student on at the front with

219 a supported peer, but that is shifting a lot of responsibility

((Noted the idea of S is unique here as peer support means shifting responsibility to the peer))

220 onto a student [and =

221 NY: [yeah

222 SG: = I don't think that's a good idea.

((SG continues to share his thought that peer support may not be a good idea))

Finally, impulsive students may need to take a break if they find themselves overwhelmed as explained in line 274 by SG. In his experience in gaming, he provided advice to gamers who have the tendency to be impulsive to take a break if overwhelmed else they may experience trauma (see L276 to L278). SG here finds some sense in his gaming experience to provide a practical solution of taking a break when a situation is overwhelming for any student specially when a student exhibits a spectrum of impulsive behaviour.

Extracted Lines 215 – 222 (Break when Overwhelmed: Impulsiveness, Part 7)

269 SG: Yeah (.) and um ::
270 and that would.
271 In the TTRPG scene, then DND there.
272 I now in my games the advice everybody to if there is a thing
273 which you are experiencing in the game that you don't want to
274 experience, then you say can we take a break or can we pause
for
(Idea of S to take a break if a student is experiencing impulsive behaviour)
275 a moment? Because obviously like the (.) the stories that we
people
276 play through are full of trauma. That's what makes a good
277 adventure story. However, there's some traumas that people
278 just don't want to have happen to them, even if it's not
279 really
280 JM: Yeah.
(Transition Relevance Place, TRP, here))

D. Conversation Covered in Appendix 4: Inclusion Strategies on Inattentive

Behaviour

The next topic that the group discussed is all about inattentiveness or tendency to be bored and daydream (IBO, 2019). In the opening lines, NY shared that the presented case mirrored on himself and inferred to as admitting to his inattentive behaviour and implicitly indicated that such was in his younger years (L309 “Hey this is me!” and L322 “you did really badly in school”). And when SG taunted NY (L321 - L322), the idea of not being nurtured came in, although SG corrected NY by saying in L327 as “Fostered!” Authors that develop inclusion practices specifically that of UDL (Ron Mace, 1980) posits that it is not the learner that should be fixed but rather fixing the environment that nurtures and creates disability (UDL Guideline, 2011, p3). It is important to proactively design to create learning environments for all students, this way learners are fostered despite their, say inattentive behaviour (IBO, 2019).

Extracted Lines 316 – 327 (Fostering: Inattentive, Part 1)

- 316 JM: OK. Inattentive.
- 317 Good.
- 318 Like get the help.
- 319 NY: Hey this is me.
- 320 To come up with something's theories and must (.) must
- 321 SG: Yeah.
- 322 Supposedly you did really badly in school, right?
- 323 NY: Yeah
- 324 But by what next impure tell you?

325 Clearly he wasn't terrible.

326 Just wasn't nurtured.

327 SG: (H) um (.) fostered (0.7)

((Transition Relevance Place, TRP, here))

The group looked at the old policy of checking diaries or daily planner as referred to in L328 -329 although JM (in context has been in school for long time) admitted that he does not use it (L333). NY (in context is a new teacher in school) finds it to be useful and suggested that it should be reintroduced (L334 - L336) to address inattentive behaviour.

Extracted Lines 328 – 336 (Diaries or Daily Planners: on Inattentive, Part 2)

328 NY: We don't have that ((referring to the check diaries))

329 JM: No, we used to.

330 NY: No, we

331: JM: we used (.)

332 we had the daily planner. All students have the book, but

333 I never use

((JM was honest enough to refer to resources such as student planners but were not used))

334 NY: but we need to reintroduce that. We need to

((NY believes that planners are useful in addressing inattentiveness))

335 <make sure that people use it/>

336 It's very useful I think

However, SG was showing reluctance and questions how the group should make sure that teachers use it (L337 – L338). JM explained that this has been done

by the Homeroom Teachers (L346). SG finds some constraints in letting teachers use the daily planner as it may end up as a mere compliance by just stamping it without really using it to address inattentiveness (L35 – L354).

Extracted Lines 337 – 358 (Commitment to Use Diaries: Inattentive, Part 3)

337 SG: How do (.)

338 you make sure that people use it, though?

((SG inquires on how to make teachers use a resource which may address inattentiveness))

339 JM: Stop. You can [start=

340 NY: [with the teachers

341 JM: = well

342 NY: this is something teachers

343 JM: also we checked before back to the [home =

344 SG: [and yeah (.) yeah

345 The one you

346 JM: =room ((referring to homeroom)) with the type we used to
classroom teacher

347 You would do.

348 Yeah. So there's

349 NY: the homeroom teacher who checked it. That's what

350 SG: yeah, that's what I was (.) most of my responsibility. Other

351 than like picking up people's glasses from, they'll delivered

352 by their own. Whatever. But what it always, eventually comes

back

353 down to is the kids who can't be honest right in their agendas

354 Don't do it properly. But I stamp it anyway because they

((Concern of S of mere compliance than making planners useful))

355 gotta get it out the door because they're about to get

356 picked up.

357 NY: Yeah.

358 SG: so (.) there is a lot of slippage (.) that happens

((compliance brought about by constraint in time))

In addressing the problem of teachers' non-use of Daily Planner (or use but out of compliance which is not meaningful) in addressing inattentiveness, SG suggested that the strategy of a whole school approach be considered. The conversation provided a grassroot perspective of teachers in the frontline which concepts may not have been ignored by the school. Based on teachers' experience, the already set policy of Daily Planner may have been assumed to have been taking place but has been ineffective. It took a conversation to discover that something was not working and the same conversation led to a practical solution of bringing everyone to be involved and commit as a matter of practice (L361 – L365).

Extracted Lines 360 – 382 (Diaries as Whole School Approach: Inattentive, Part 4)

360 JM: uhm

361 NY: so like this to get it. And it needs to be a whole

362 school routine

((Solution offered by N is whole school approach))

363 SG: yeah

((Transition Relevance Place, TRP, here))

364 NY: not just like.

365 whole school routine not just MYP directive or PYP

366 don't manage it and then it just gets

367 left behind.

368 Needs to be host thing and I come out applicant like

369 SG: there could be. I

370 mean in theory you could have a (.) uhm (.) a (.)

371 and our website, [all the students access =

372 JM: [there could be

373 SG: = and we just upload it to that

374 I'm

375 NY: Right.

376 JM: and it's probably, I mean it, it ended up

377 NY: it doesn't supply.

378 I think [that =

379 SG: [Umm

380 NY: = will be good.

381 If you don't get printed version, get something they can

382 use and pay attention.

Finally, in inattentive behaviour, NY and SG find providing positive feedback to be effective should focus on contribution to qualify in solving inattentiveness (L432 and L436-L438). Also, feedback should not merely be praising for the sake of praising, but feedback should be something that the learner understands (L431 and L442). Indeed, inattentive behaviour may be caused by something that is bothering the learner and if the feedback is something that the learner can comprehend, then it

motivates him to respond (IBO, 2019) which NY was actually referring to in L431 – L433.

Extracted Lines 427 – 449 (Providing Positive Feedback: Inattentive, Part 5)

427 we do that (.)

428 JM: Nice (.) really

429 NY: facing front feedback.

430 JM: I do (.) I do that a lot (.) but try [to

431 NY: [Yeah, I don't understand

432 feedback in the classroom (.) Like, if (.) if someone's given an answer.

((N provides a solution to inattentiveness by providing feedback))

433 and it's not (.) It's they have to go

434 SG: No (.) Yeah (.) for sure

435 NY: So you (.) you praise that

436 SG: but the point is to establish that you can even work with

437 anything as long as, as long as there's a carefully

438 considered (.) contribution.

439 NY: because even incorrect answer is still takes [off (.) one option =

440 SG: [Yeah

441 NY: = building those. It's great response.

442 Antarctica pleated (.) that's my problem [great =

((concern of N is providing praise for the sake of it))

443 JM: [yeah (.) yeah(.) me too

444 NY: = on top of it (.) but formatives in the classroom like

445 anecdotal feedback face to face feedback.
446 fine with that/
447 JM: yeah (.) yeah(.) the same. I think we're just overwhelmed
448 with (.) really (.) insane (.)
449 OK, I think that's the final (.) I think I can actually stop the

recording now

((Transition Relevance Place,TRP, here))

In an online environment, there is a limited contact with students: hence, leaving written accurate and helpful feedback has become more important. Tone and intentionality must be considered as the social and emotional function of feedback are well valued by students (Kennette, 2021). This is an anxiety-reducer and emotion-regulator according to Rowe (2011). This is because positive feedback given in a socially isolated situation creates an excellent connection between teacher and students who are in a distance learning setting.

Chapter V RESEARCH RESULTS

Results and Discussion

The reason why it is difficult to wrap one's mind about the idea of inclusion is that people look at students who have extreme cases of disability (mental or physical) and then people are told that they may be teachers, but they are not trained to handle students with special needs (Chan, 2015).

This mindset is reinforced by actual experiences of teachers in BINUS SCHOOL Simprug when for example, a student starts yelling, if not kicking facilities in school or worse would physically hurt other students (or himself/herself) to the end of

disrupting class time. The poor teacher has to stop teaching and give more attention to an individual who is having episode of say autism, ADHD, ADD, Dyslexia etc. in order to mitigate the effect of the student's behaviour and shield all others against such effect – which for many other students, this is unacceptable as they are expecting the teacher to cater to the greater good of others who are in class (BINUS Report, 2022).

Then the school says, “no problem”. “IB provided strategies on how to handle the situation” but in the practical sense, the strategies are too general and may not even have an effect when applied to the situation at hand. Then the teacher is blamed for not applying inclusion in his or her class.

More so when students are online where there is no way for the teacher to see what is going on at the student's home. There is no authority present to implement inclusive strategies that may be available, unless the parents would take the role of the authority and are committed and dedicated to implement inclusive procedure – which is not always the case.

Therefore, it is important to go deeper into knowing the perspectives of teachers on how they make sense of inclusion practices and see how these strategies may be applicable and be effective.

Practices Promoting Inclusivity

In studying the teaching practices in one of the International Baccalaureate (IB) schools in Indonesia that foster inclusivity, an ethnomethodological approach was used. The data collected were based on the social reality at a “level where it is constructed – meaning, the data were taken from the very concrete realm of action and interaction” (Leiter, 1980). To do this, a close examination of the practical details

of everyday activities of teachers and on how they make decisions (Trace,2016) have to be taken into consideration.

The conversation in Appendix 1 (L001 – L033) provided context of the interaction among three western teacher participants: JM who has been with BINUS SCHOOL Simprug (Jakarta) for sixteen (16) years while serving as the Head of the IB DP English Department while NY and SG, although new to the institution are experienced English Teachers who had been teaching in other schools. The three were reviewing the policy on how to handle students who are hyperactive (L034 – L157 in Appendix 2), impulsive (L158 – L315 in Appendix 3), and inattentive (L316 – L449 in Appendix 4) - all behaviours of which need to be addressed when implementing IB's required program development plan on inclusive education (IBO Report, 2022).

Inclusive Practices to Address Hyperactive Behaviour

There were three matters that were discussed by the participants about hyperactivity among students: representation (specifically on movement), actions taken by the teacher (referring to fidgeting and spinners) and the concept of time-out area (addressing the coping mechanism of hyperactive students).

In the Appendix 2 conversation, teachers have to agree on how hyperactive should be represented which is more of various activities where the student can move. The teachers were aware that hyperactive students have energy that can be channeled and used in positive way through empowering them to help with the teachers' teaching (L056) instead of dealing with disruption in class.

As for students who are fidgety, the teachers have to understand that students increase their attention and alertness when they fidget (Hartanto, 2016). As mentioned

in the IBO report (2019), doodling, drawing or playing stress ball help students focus on task given whether online or offline. Although there is little research that says spinners, as a fidget tool, are effective (Calfas, 2017), one of the participants admit that spinner works for him as he himself has hyperactive disorder when he was younger. Hyperactive students just need to focus on something that they find meaning and preventing them from doing so, aggravates their disruption of the class. The “spinners” they suggested have been very effective as these redirect the learner’s energy and enthusiasm to something that physically moves.

When a student is set to a time-out corner as a strategy to curtail behaviour, teachers observed that this is counterproductive. It does not help further the learner since “standing in the corner” does not produce any output for the learner or when on a virtual classroom, no parent is there to take the role of a teacher to oversee the student. The teachers agreed on this approach which helps hyperactive students cope up with challenging situations and in effect contributes to a healthy, productive classroom environment.

Inclusive Practices to Address Impulsive Behaviour

Four important points were raised by the participants here: Safety (to include actions such as use of timer and explicit and frequent discussion of expectations and consequences), Sarcasm (teachers being considerate), Peer Support (taken as a burden on students to be given such a responsibility) and Taking a Break (when overwhelmed go for gaming).

As far as impulsive behaviour in the Appendix 3 is concerned, the participants instantly tackled the issue of safety based on their experience. Impulsive students have the tendency to be unaware of “danger” that may be encountered in school, in

this case, laboratory hazards. Impulsive students have no control on how they would react. Nonetheless, there was a need to continue to be explicit in reminding students of the rules (including the consequences) – not just once but have to be done regularly and consistently. The teachers in the study admitted that impulsive students may not follow safety protocols: hence the teachers' practical strategy was to outline the consequences if safety rules are breached. The teachers opined that timer would be helpful to do away with danger as it serves as a reminder to focus on the task on hand (Bennett, 2018).

Another problem that was discussed was teachers' use of sarcasm, which may be demeaning and triggers emotional outbursts among impulsive students. According to Pickering (2018), negative emotional impact of a message is enhanced, rather than muted, using sarcasm: hence the participants believe that teacher have to be sensitive enough not to be sarcastic (even though they may run out of patience as noted by one of the participants).

Based on the transcript, delegating the responsibility of taking care of impulsive students to their classmates is burdensome. The participants opined that there is a negative implication when other students are asked to take the role of peer support but are given that responsibility to curtail the effect of impulsiveness of a special needs student. The school needs to review this policy. However, Pickens-Cantrell (2016) in her research says that peer support increases positive social interaction for students with special needs.

Finally, when overwhelmed, teachers who are gamers themselves suggest that it is practical for impulsive students to take a pause or a break, just like in the game. One of the participants shared his experience as he himself is suffering from being impulsive when he was much younger, and gaming was his way to take a break when

overwhelmed. Foreman (2021) agreed with the concept. According to her research, control-based games indeed would help students with their coping mechanism.

Inclusive Practices to Address Inattentive Behaviour

Addressing inattentive behaviour was partially discussed given the time for teachers to collaborate hence, the discussion was limited only to planners (for students to organize themselves) and teachers providing positive feedback.

While reviewing the teaching practices in addressing inclusion, teachers realized that one simple way of approaching inattentive behaviour (Appendix 4) is the use of a Daily Planner. In general, this planner serves as an organiser for the student. This can be used to assist the student in keeping tabs of schoolwork, expectations, and schedules (Panicker, 2016). At times this Daily Planner is not being optimised, students do not have the due diligence in using it, because teachers themselves are not committed to ask students to use it. The group suggested that a successful implementation would require a whole school approach instead of adapting its use by some teachers, while others do not, does not give a united approach to the students.

Providing positive feedback is an anxiety-reducer and emotion-regulator for inattentive students doing tasks whether online or offline (Rowe, 2011). However, the group qualified that the feedback given to inattentive student must be something that the learner understands and can comprehend with so that there is motivation to respond (IBO, 2019). According to Kennette (2021), tone and intentionality of feedback are valued by inattentive students.

School's Perspective Underlying the Practices

According to its educational principle, BINUS SCHOOL Simprug values every student. Should there be any barriers to learning, it is willing to address it in order to allow all students to reach their potential (IBO Report, 2022).

The school's perspective on inclusivity that defines the above practices cited by the participants is one that recognizes diversity and the unique contributions and experiences of all (emphasis on "all") students whether it is on an online or offline setting. All students are respected and included and the school commits itself to creating this inclusive learning environment.

This perspective is often reflected in the school's mission statement and policies and is reinforced through Professional Development (PD) and training for teachers and staff. As for the school, the cited practical conversations which are being developed and practiced by teachers to foster inclusivity, find its guidance from the school's mission which is "positioning every Binusian at the heart of what we do" (IBO Report 2022). This point of view entails students to set challenging goals, teachers to remove identified barriers to learning, and the school to review related policies that create a culture of inclusive education so that every student will reach his or her full potential (IBO Report, 2022).

As the school goes for online class setting, it continues to adhere with the belief that teachers must value every student and inclusive education must start from within. This was evident by the discussion of the participants specifically when one of them admitted that he himself has been either inattentive, hyperactive if not impulsive and should be fostered (Line 322) and it is important to design and create learning environments where learners are nurtured. According to Mace (1980), those that develop inclusion practices posits that it is not the learner that should be fixed but rather the fixing the environment that nurtures and creates disability. The school

confirms this belief: hence it allowed teachers to look into the practices that may improve if not make the procedure effective when it comes to making the school inclusive.

The school conform to the IB principle of re-constructing its academic environment (teaching and learning) so that it may accommodate the learning disabilities of students for behaviours (of which these learners have no control). Teachers and the school must eliminate unnecessary barriers in an online learning environment without compromising academic rigour: hence, inclusion strategies have to go deeper than merely looking at physical or virtual access to the classroom but rather focus on all aspects of learning (UDL Guide, 2011).

For example, in dealing with hyperactiveness where it involved time-out corner, it is the point of view of the school that providing learning support if it is needed (IBO Report, 2022) must be part of the school's inclusive practices. Falling short of not having guidance counsellor when needed the most is a disservice to students within the school. In case where class is online, it is still a school's policy that said learning support team be readily available on call by the concerned teacher, parent if not the student himself.

The school has established policies, clear cut procedures which guide teachers and have become part of the routine on dealing with behaviours of students daily. Such guidelines became an everyday exercise for teachers such that it has become like "second skin" to the teachers that when they encounter incidents in the classroom, they act and react spontaneously based on their stock knowledge, both general and specialized, at their disposal (Cicourel, 1995).

Teachers' collective experiences in their social environment which is the classroom contribute to enriching the strategies in dealing with inclusion practices that

nurture inclusivity. These perspectives have been captured using conversation analysis and such understanding is intelligible worthy of being shared with other researchers (Garfinkel, 1999). This enriches the knowledge about inclusive practices that makes sense to educators and also that of the school administrators.

Chapter VI RESEARCH IMPLICATIONS

Summary of Findings

“Education is enhanced by the creation of affirmative, responsive environments that promote a sense of belonging, safety, self-worth and whole growth for every student” (IBO 2019).

This is International Baccalaureate’s (IB) principle when it comes to the implementation of inclusive education for all IB Schools around the world. IB defined inclusivity as increasing access and engagement for every student (IBO, 2015). It covers learners who may not necessarily have autism or attention deficit disorder etc. but merely exhibiting a bit of behaviour that is within the spectrum of such disorder or disorders. In March 2020, schools were forced to adapt to online teaching and learning following the COVID-19 Pandemic. For IB Teachers, integrating inclusion strategies became more challenging. BINUS SCHOOL Simprug, one among the IB Schools in Jakarta, Indonesia went ahead in making Inclusion as part of its Program Development Plan not just in compliance to IB’s Standards and Practices which was assessed during the Three Programme Evaluation Visit in May 2022 (IB Evaluators Report, 2022), but also to address how teachers may provide various options for presenting information, students’ demonstration of knowledge and skills, and student engagement in an online class setting. Teachers have their own mechanisms in

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dealing with everyday instructions specifically on how they make sense of the practices they developed but were taken for granted. If research is right that teachers value inclusion yet it works for some but not for others, then in this research, this sense making mechanism of western teachers working in an Indonesian international school is needed in getting further perspectives.

This study focused on the following research questions:

1. What teaching practices do western teachers in an international school aim to foster inclusivity? and
2. What is the perspective of the school on inclusivity that defines those practices?

As a response, to explore how teachers' actual ordinary and mundane discussion produce an answer as to how they (the teachers) make inclusion happen, the study considered an ethnomethodological qualitative approach. The study looked at conversation of western international teachers at the above school as many among sets of research did not cover points of view of inclusive education practitioners on how they are making sense of policies brought forward by the school and are expecting them (the teachers) to implement such policies.

The sequences were taken from an audio-visual recording of an English Department meeting, transcription of which was the one used for analysis. The three participants were western international IB school teachers, i.e., JM is from Canada while SG and NY are both from United Kingdom.

The conversation covered the following:

Appendix 1 (L001 – L033) provided context of the interaction.

Appendix 2 (L034 – L157) looked at how to deal with hyperactive students.

Appendix 3 (L158 – L315) has the topic on students being impulsive, and

Appendix 4 (L316 – L449) discussed about inattentive students.

All of the above behaviours addressed the implementation of IB's required program development plan on inclusive education (IBO Report, 2022).

In summary, ten inclusive practices that make sense to teachers in making inclusion happen (which may have been overlooked in the policy) in an online learning setting are as follows, to wit,

Point 1. Every time there is an online class, teacher must not label students based on psychological or medical diagnostic because it does not provide sound indications of student's potential. The teaching strategies must be set on how teachers may move students to reach their potential every time teaching and learning is happening in an online setting.

Point 2. Teachers must find ways and means to make the online learning environment conducive for students to feel safe and comfortable by treating distance education learners with respect and kindness as the class celebrates diversity and acknowledging each student's unique strength and abilities.

Point 3. Although time-out area can be so difficult in an online learning class, the teacher may opt to ask someone from the student's home to be an authority to support. Time-out is positive, respectful strategy which may be used for an online student who is beginning to lose self-control to regain it and get back to his or her lesson.

Point 4. In an online setting, same as when students are into a face-to-face classroom where learners may be losing attention, fidgeting or doodling provides increased alertness because the movement becomes an outlet of unexpressed energy: hence, it enables students to pay attention more (based on the experience of one of the participants).

Point 5. The use of timer is a strategy to remind impulsive learners for them to focus on what is going on either around them or factors that surrounds the completion of the task at hand.

Point 6. Online teachers have to be very explicit on rules to all most specially for students who are exhibiting impulsiveness. Expectations and consequences have to be reiterated all the time so that it will mitigate in breaching rules.

Point 7. Online teachers must avoid sarcasm when teaching. It may be effective to provoke discussion but for a student who is isolated in a distance learning mode, the negative emotional impact is enhanced, and the good intention is actually muted.

Point 8. Student would need to take a break to reset their minds when they find the tasks to be overwhelming. Like gaming according to a participant in the study, it would be a good advice to take a break else the student may experience a trauma.

Point 9. Teachers may ask online learners to use daily planner in addressing inattentiveness as it will help student be on task: however, this will be more effective if the whole school does this practice to make it as part of their culture.

Point 10. Online teachers must provide not just feedback but leaving written accurate and helpful feedback with good tone and intentionality for online learners appreciate whatever they have completed. It is also a way for teachers and students who are separated to connect. Timely feedback is an anxiety-reducer in a socially isolated situation.

It should also be noted that there are dissenting opinion that needs to be highlighted. For example, a participant questioned the inclusive practice of having hyperactive student to be placed under “Time-out” in a corner as they find it counterproductive. It does not help further the learner since “standing in the corner” does not produce any output for the learner. Hyperactive students just need to focus

on something that they find meaning and preventing them from doing so, aggravates their disruption of the class. One practical way is to let a hyperactive student use “spinners” as these redirect the learner’s energy and enthusiasm to something that physically moves. The teachers agreed on this approach which helps hyperactive students cope up in challenging situations and in effect contributes to a healthy, productive classroom environment.

As a matter of improving the strategy in dealing with impulsive students on the other hand, teachers must be conscious that they are susceptible to safety issues and for inattentive students, the school has to bring back the practice of using diaries or journals – all of which were not included in the procedure set forth in the school’s inclusion policy but were unearthed using ethnomethodological study.

According to the school, its perspective that defines the above practices is taken from the context of its Vision and Mission statement, i.e., “positioning every [student] at the heart of what we do” and it emphasizes the word “every”. This means that teachers have to provide access and remove barriers to learning so that online students may reach their full potential despite being on a distance education mode of learning. The school has established policies and clear cut procedures yet there were those that have been overlooked but such gaps were identified in the findings as teachers implement inclusive education in school.

Conclusion

The central value of the findings in this research is that western teachers’ reflexive accountability contributed to the orderliness and shared performance to carry out inclusive education in an online learning environment. No amount of training or policy will help in implementing inclusion unless the school is the one that will adapt to

changes that will allow removal of barriers and increasing access for learners in a distance education mode.

The purpose of the research is to understand the teachers' implicit belief in justifying their actions and inferences on how they make inclusion happen in their classrooms whether online or offline. Seasoned teachers, the same as other professionals, remarkably have at their disposal a stock of knowledge that they rely on in dealing with everyday life (Cicourel, 1995). For example, they can identify what may be considered strange or unusual and what is normal or right because of their accumulated background knowledge (Meehan, 1980) and then settle concerns, solve problems or implement tasks that make sense to them. Cuff (2003) calls this as "common sense attitude" under which teachers operate in their daily life and at work.

This study involves teachers' sense-making and will not be concerned with scientific attitude which deals with finding out something but rather the study will be more on knowledge that enables the fulfilment of practical task (Cuff, 2008) such as fostering inclusivity and the practices that may not necessarily be in the written policy as these sense making information may have been taken for granted or just implied and as such were not captured in the said written policy. These practices are borne from experience and day-to-day encounters of teachers with their students, making every situation distinctly different from each other.

People, including teachers, have the natural attitude that triggers experiences and makes possible for them to act and react in a social setting (Trace, 2016). In order to authentically capture these unwritten practices of sense making, the study made use of conversation analysis (instead of interview or survey method) because the very taken-for-granted nature of sense-making activities means that the informants or participants to the study will be resistant to analytic discovery of interview and survey

(Pollner and Emerson, 2001). In this regard, for purposes of transparency, the study relied on video recording and analysed the conversation of participants using Jefferson Transcription System (2004).

Implication and Recommendation

The knowledge derived from interaction of teachers may be trivial to some but the impact of the findings when analyzed would be reason why implementation of inclusion becomes more effective. Seasoned educators, such as western international teachers, remarkably have at their disposal a stock knowledge that they can rely on in dealing with everyday life (Cicourel, 1995). This sense-making process may not be concerned with scientific attitude rather such knowledge may enable them to fulfill a practical task (Cuff, 2008) such as fostering inclusivity that may not be found in the official policy.

As part of this study's assumption, the ethnomethodological perspective which relates to sense-making lies in the social world of accommodating multiple realities: hence, the findings here would be unique and distinct because different observers may see the world in different ways (Vom Lehn, 2014). Reiterating, in ethnomethodology, the meanings of objects are never fixed, instead objects have different meanings for different people in different situations (Vom Lehn, 2014). Because of these variations, it is recommended that further analysis of other teachers' discussion be evaluated as an extension to this study but contained within the same international school if not expanded to other international schools.

Further, the conversation was limited to a discussion about a spectrum of behaviour that would require inclusive strategies but because inclusion embraces not just those experiencing learning difficulties, a further study may go for broader

definition of inclusion other than increasing access and engagement in learning for all students by identifying and removing barriers, such as gender equality and so on.

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APPENDICES

APPENDIX 01

English Department Collaborative Session
(Introduction on Inclusion Strategies to address Hyperactive, Impulsive and
Inattentive Student Behaviour during an Online Learning in BINUS SCHOOL
Simprug)

Transcription re 13 April 2022 13:30h – 14:10h English Department Meeting

Letter Used to Represent Participant:

JM – [REDACTED] (Subjects Taught: English A, Theory of Knowledge
and Psychology)

SM – [REDACTED] (Subjects Taught: English A, English B, Theory of
Knowledge)

NY – [REDACTED] (Subjects Taught: English A, Theory of
Knowledge)

All teachers above are westerners (i.e., from Canada and UK)

NB: This is introduction to conversations in appendices 2, 3 and 4, i.e., J clarified that although ADD (Attention-Deficit-Disorder) or ADHD (Attention-Deficit-and-Hyperactivity-Disorder) were touched, it does not mean that all students have such disorder and that teachers should apply special needs strategies (assuming that J was made aware that teachers have not been trained to be Special Needs educators. However, in a seemingly kind of a monologue, J clarified that they are supposed to discuss on how to address students who may have exhibited any behaviour within the spectrum of ADD or ADHD and not to diagnose students. This concept (of teachers' role of not diagnosing students but should focus on students' behaviour within the spectrum of ADD and/or ADHD that may have been exhibited by students in general) was not taken into account in the Inclusion Policy (which was finalized months after this group's session) but was uncovered in this conversation analysis.

JM however made mention that the meeting was more of the inclusion strategic practices of teachers in BINUS SCHOOL Simprug (based on perspectives of the above-mentioned teachers).

Time: 13.30.00h – 13.32.31h (2min and 31 second conversation on context of the discussion).

001 J: We are now being recorded. Yeah. Turn off the transcription ((the three teachers are having virtual meeting and J, who is leading the collaborative session using Microsoft Teams (MsTeams) Video Meet Recording feature, was disabling the transcription feature. The actual transcription presented in the thesis as part of the data was re-generated by playing the same video in MsTeams and activating the transcription feature. The generated output was reviewed by the author and using the basic Jefferson Transcription System, the author annotated the regenerated transcription))

002 S: ok

003 J: I know (.) stop transcription

004 Ok (.) let's begin (.) so last week we::

005 I mean we looked at behaviours (.) I guess a (.)

006 umm (.) associated with autism

007 in a more general kind of way (.) Today we're doing basically it's (.) the same activity, but

008 we're looking at behaviour associated with ADHD ADD. But

009 we're in no way diagnosing our students (.) you know, we're just

010 looking at the behaviours and then possible things that we can

011 do or you know (.) looking at challenges that might arise and

012 then possible ways that we can deal with those challenges.

013 Again:: NOT (.) not diagnosing.
((S and N were listening as shown on screen))

014 So I (.) I don't know if there's any need to go into ADHD and ADD in

015 the difference and all of that.
((Transition Relevance Place, or TRP here))

016 um (.) I miss Vinitha's ((One of the English Teachers)) being excused

017 so it's only the three of us (.) so probably (.) I went through this activity on Monday (.)

018 so I think (.) we'll (.) we'll go through (.) there's only actually three scenarios (0.8)

019 and so if :: you maybe (.) you 2 can then talk about issues that

020 you've encountered and then and then strategies that you would

021 do (.) as follow up (.) and then I will:: give my two cents as well.

022 So the (.) the three behaviours that we're looking at are

023 hyperactivity (.) impulsiveness and inattentiveness (.) Again, in a

024 general (.) way (.) not (.) not specifically related to ADHD.

025 So let's get into it. Maybe just take a 20 second (.) and (.) and
026 read this (10.0)
 ((a slide is shown showing a cartoon illustration of a boy who is away
from the group and tumbling while his classmates and the teacher are seated in a
circle formation on the floor))
 ((Transition Relevance Place, or TRP here))

027 So maybe Sam, we can start with you :: issues with hyperactivity (.)
028 Now if (.) if there are other things that you do, please (.) please let
029 us know.

030 S: So just before I (.) I before I start talking about the teaching
031 strategies, the:: just a comment on the representation of
032 hyperactivity, the (.) the cartoon kid is obviously doing hands down
033 and so on.

(No TRP here; but Turn Construction Units, TCU and TRPs can be found in Appendix 02 for continuation of the conversation).

-end of appendix 01-

APPENDIX 02

English Department Collaborative Session (Inclusion Strategies to address Hyperactive Student Behaviour during an Online Learning in BINUS SCHOOL Simprug)

Transcription re 13 April 2022 13:30h – 14:10h English Department Meeting

Letter Used to Represent Participant:

JM – [REDACTED] (Subjects Taught: English A, Theory of Knowledge and Psychology)

SG – [REDACTED] (Subjects Taught: English A, English B, Theory of Knowledge)

NY – [REDACTED] (Subjects Taught: English A, Theory of Knowledge)

All teachers above are westerners (i.e., from Canada, UK and Australia)

NB: The conversation provided the perspectives of three teachers as regards to their inclusion strategic practices to address students who are hyperactive (a spectrum of ADHD) which were not found in the policy. For example, using positive energy in a positive way by including the hyperactivity of the student as part of the class activity: however, it may not always work as others may do the same and it may end up being destructive rather than constructive. Another example is that the school provided a policy of time-out corner, yet S and N finds it punitive and may not provide a positive impact on the student although J offered the counselor's office as the time-out place.

Time: 13.32.18h – 13.37.32h (5min and 14 second conversation on Inclusion Strategies in dealing with Hyperactive student)

034 So maybe Sam, we can start with you :: issues with hyperactivity (.)

035 Now if (.) if there are other things that you do, please (.) please let

036 us know.

037 S: So just before I (.) I before I start talking about the teaching

038 strategies, the:: just a comment on the representation of

039 hyperactivity, the (.) the cartoon kid is obviously doing hands down

040 and so on.

041 Umm.

042 It doesn't have to be so obvious, right? There are lots

043 of different ways a person can be hyperactive, but not be

044 cartoonishly so/
045 And ::
046 SO (.)
047 The :
048 The things which I will be drawn to here would be :: <explicitly>
049 teaching modes of behaviour (.) because I like the idea of
050 empowering a student to recognize what's affecting them.
051 [umm
052 J: [I'm sorry, is it this explicitly I need to
053 S: [Yeah. Yeah, not necessarily.
054 <It immediately in reaction to somebody being structured because of
hyperactivity,
055 but just, um (.)
056 generally incorporating that into your, um (.) um teaching method.
057 Umm (.)
058 And (.)
059 I can see you for younger kids.
060 Uh. Using excess energy in a positive way might be:: might be
061 more valuable than for our kids.
062 [Uh::
063 J: yeah.
(Transition Relevance Place, TRP, here))
064 S: And then the: :
065 A comment on the timeout facility in my previous school./
066 One of our students did need a place to go and just vent.
067 Well, I didn't see it being that helpful to him in particular. So

((S here finds the school strategy on time-out corner as not helpful))

068 ummh

069 I don't know if it's the kind of thing that could just be always

070 [used for.

071 J: [But and one is OCD actually and (.) and he knew that he had, he

072 could go to the guidance counselor's office for his

073 timeout.

((J provided an alternative of going to counselor's office as place for time-out))

074 S: uhhm

075 J: I think we've done that with a few students, but he's the only

076 one that would (.) There were times I was OK

077 Student.

078 I think you better get up and go and he would. He would get up

079 and he go.

080 He would act and nods.

081 So and what was intentionally spit. It wasted me on his own.

082 S: [umm

083 J: [But he goes to the bathroom water on this.

084 S: Yeah.

085 J: Yeah, yeah.

086 S: Well, that and that's the that's the important thing that we're

087 talking about in general, is providing students with coping

088 mechanisms that will be healthy and helpful that they can carry

089 into their adult lives.

090 J: I don't know if I want. [I'm hate this I like =

091 S: [Yeah, yeah.

092 J: = Like foreigner.
 ((J is highlighting in the slide that was presented "Time -out corner"))

093 S: Umm.

094 J: That's great. ((Grade 11)) Eleven.

095 S: Yeah.
 ((Transition Relevance Place, TRP, here))

096 N: I (.) I say loud.

097 [Like you =

098 J: [Well, yeah,

099 N: = it's not distracting me. They've got one

100 of those spinners (.) I see you've [got one =

101 S: [Yeah.

102 N: = Questions through

103 do (.) do something. Is very creative output.

104 And I do all the time.

105 It helps me focus my [ideas =

106 J: [yeah.

107 N: = Uh, and it helps them. So I'm hopeful that I don't think the

108 timeout corner works. I don't think it's affected it's

109 isolatory (.) [It's =
 ((N finds the school's idea of time-out likewise to be not useful as it is
 isolatory))

110 J: [no

111 N: = I think it's like.

112 I (.) [speak.

113 J: [Yeah, yeah

114 S: Needs to be a positive place rather than a
 ((S also raised the issue of a positive place, not in policy, rather than a
 punitive place))

115 place that you go because we've [messed up.

116 N: [You guided. Mm-hmm.

117 N: No (.) side (.) do I (.) I sit down with them.

118 Hyperactivity. And I tried to help them focus on it. It's (.) it's (.)

119 not on this list, strangely.
 ((N also provides the idea of sitting down with them which was not in
 the policy))

120 umm (.) Suppose it being the (.) Well, that's fine. That's becoming
 destructive

121 Even so quick, because that (.) [that's =

122 J: [yeah

123 N: = Maybe they'll be ashamed.

124 So what I do is (.) I acknowledge it and then I go sit with them

125 Normally (.) How things are a bit difficult.
 ((Transition Relevance Place, TRP, here))

126 S: There's a certain amount of automatic mimicking behaviour

127 that you can kind of use to your advantage there as well. If

128 somebody extremely full of energy and you just go and be

129 very, very calm, they might just start to do that as well.
 ((S introduced the idea of hyperactive student mimicking calmness of
 the teacher))

130 J: Yeah (1.0)
 ((Transition Relevance Place, TRP, here))

131 N: I don't know if it's done in the past (.) and I don't know if it works in
 every

132 case (.) I've actually copied their behavior a little bit or not

133 copy, but kind of (.7)

134 Copy [that =

135 S: [umm

136 N: = OK, so if they if they are being they, they've got they're like

137 champagne like ready and I tried to.

138 That answer explain it. I tried to integrate unless.

139 Look, I thought the full engaged. [So =

140 S: [channel what they =

141 have into [the

142 = [creatively and maybe that I can make something

143 productive out of that hyperactivity (.)
 ((N and S talk about engaging the into his class activity to use that energy
 become productive))

144 J: Well that would be excess energy.
 ((Transition Relevance Place, TRP, here))

145 N: It doesn't always work.
 ((N acknowledges that integrating the energy of the student in lesson may not
 work))

146 S: umm

147 N: And you really need to get classroom for that one

148 otherwise.

149 And go very wrong.

150 S: umm

151 N: I did that.

152 J: Yeah.

153 N: So because I thought you

154 want me to kick as well. So this one kid who defines it still.

155 Alright. OK, let's do something (.)

156 uhmm (.) Can be infectious/
 ((N thinks that other kids may do the same, e.g. kicking the chair - infectious))

157 J: And the next one ((referring to the next behaviour/next topic)
((Transition Relevance Place, TRP, here))

(may have TRP here; but Turn Construction Units, TCU and TRPs can be found in Appendix 03 for continuation of the conversation).

-end of appendix 02-

APPENDIX 03

English Department Collaborative Session
(Inclusion Strategies to address Impulsive Student Behaviour during an Online Learning in BINUS SCHOOL Simprug)

Transcription re 13 April 2022 13:30h – 14:10h English Department Meeting

Letter Used to Represent Participant:

JM – [REDACTED] (Subjects Taught: English A, Theory of Knowledge and Psychology)

SG – [REDACTED] (Subjects Taught: English A, English B, Theory of Knowledge)

NY – [REDACTED] (Subjects Taught: English A, Theory of Knowledge)

All teachers above are westerners (i.e., from Canada, UK and Australia)

NB: The conversation provided the perspectives of three teachers as regards to their inclusion strategic practices to address students who are impulsive (a spectrum of ADHD) which were not found in the policy. For example, peer support was not actually taken well as teachers are shifting responsibility to the peer: however, the group agreed with having group support system as an alternative as part of the Inclusion Strategy in dealing with Impulsive Behaviour. Another example is that there may be safety rules which an Impulsive student may transgress but is not aware of the consequences: hence, such rules have to be discussed and explicitly demonstrated in class. There is a discussion on use of trauma which is used in games for students to remember as they don't want that trauma to happen to them. Finally, a practice of the teacher to take a break if a student is experiencing impulsive behavior may help everyone in the class.

Time: 13.37.31h – 13.44.27h (6min and 56 second conversation on Inclusion Strategies in dealing with Impulsive behaviour of students)

158 J: OK, next one.
((next one refers to J presenting his next slide which is about impulsive behaviour))

159 [Cancel this.

160 S: [Y::es (0.8)

161 N: Umm, ignoring danger (.) you've been very loose.

162 I don't (o.8)

163 Reminds me up earlier. Umm, well it this morning. Danger or not,

164 I'm not sure it's extended. I'm sure it works. You imagine science

165 And then what?

166 J: Umm
((N is looking at the strategy of safety: hence the remark ignoring danger in science laboratories))

167 N: but somewhere to interrupt this and what's out of town. And

168 I just have to remind them of their place. But in a very

169 polite and like manner.

170 Using a timer, [I was like

171 J: [when I with CL safely in terms of.

172 it's got umm

173 Course meals.

174 For one, one particular that I'm trying to show up.

175 N: No.

176 J: Sexist and stuff, and that's what I thought. Like out of safe.

177 S: That's one good to me as well. Yeah.

178 N: Possible boundaries.

179 J: Ohh yeah. I mean. And the there was green.

180 Yeah (.) It sort of you.

181 Don't see this case. It [was a solo =

182 S: [umm

183 J: = I have to look.

184 And

185 And just say, hey, remember years ago. But I remember

186 students who were in the computer lab.

187 And he's walking (.) Extra (.)

188 I like that idea (.) What I see

189 And :: and this is really what you for every system of the meeting.

213 J: [yeah.

214 And yeah, it's sarcastic
 ((Transition Relevance Place, TRP, here))

215 N: = support works using groups
 ((N was referring to the strategy item D which is 'arranging for peer support'))

216 J: yeah.

217 S: One thing I'll point out about using peer support and the
 218 video (.) it's suggested seating the student on at the front with
 219 a supported peer, but that is shifting a lot of responsibility
 ((Noted the idea of S is unique here as peer support means shifting
 responsibility to the peer))

220 onto a student [and =

221 N: [yeah

222 S: = I don't think that's a good idea.
 ((S continues to share his thought that peer support may not be a good idea))

223 N: But that's why [I prefer

224 J: [I think =

225 S: Yeah (.) Group system (.)
 ((S thinks that alternative to peer support is Group Support System))
 ((Transition Relevance Place, TRP, here))

226 J: = I think they're talking about like in like, students who definitely
 227 have ADHD. And I brought this up, I think Oh
 228 yeah, this is this. Edward, the use of the timer and (.) and my
 229 comment was, you know, this would probably be a case (.) you had two
 230 teachers so you had to meet.
 231 That the national teaching deals with students like this.
 232 The other student should more or less
 233 Do they all of this?

234 S: umm

235 J: And that, and it's professionally planned out. It's

236 [it's kind of =

237 S: [a little thrown in there (.) yeah

238 J: = Yeah
((Transition Relevance Place, TRP, here))

239 S: peer support
((back to peer support))

240 J: and that's like, yes.

241 And you know, I think.

242 It would be done in a proper and professional [what =

243 S: [Yes

244 J: Yeah
((Transition Relevance Place, TRP, here))

245 Yes.

246 S: Some of the solutions proposed in the video are really

247 ideal world solutions and
((S noted that the strategies or solutions were ideal world solutions insinuating that it may not work in the real world))

248 J: but they might be like that video

249 might be for that type of environment where again you have

250 those two features this trip

251 S: that's right

252 J: Maybe.

253 S: Not that ((pointing to upper line of the slide))

254 Yeah, explicit discussion of safety is (.) never gonna go on
((back to safety, S believes that this must be explicitly discussed apparently in class))

255 this. Right.

256 N: Well, I was just gonna mention that because with
257 outward, Andrew discuss some pretty big news challenging. So
258 we can see a EX boundaries and it's just as simple as a dude
259 transgressed boundary is going to be serious ramifications for
((N followed up explicit safety rules that if not followed, there are serious
consequences))
260 [them.
261 J: [And it's. Yeah.
262 Religion.
263 N: Absolutely
264 J: Respect.
265 I don't want to turn this into like (.) God exists. No, he doesn't!
266 Yes, he does. Well,
267 N: but you're referring to Oliver
268 J: Yeah (h)
((J raised the issue that students may question the rules; used analogy to
religion))
((Transition Relevance Place, TRP, here))
269 S: Yeah (.) and um ::
270 and that would.
271 In the TTRPG scene, then DND there.
272 I now in my games the advice everybody to if there is a thing
273 which you are experiencing in the game that you don't want to
274 experience, then you say can we take a break or can we pause for
((Idea of S to take a break if a student is experiencing impulsive behaviour))
275 a moment? Because obviously like the (.) the stories that we people
276 play through are full of trauma. That's what makes a good
277 adventure story. However, there's some traumas that people

278 just don't want to have happen to them, even if it's not
279 really

280 J: Yeah.
(Transition Relevance Place, TRP, here))

281 S: And I think that's a good (.) so like :: mentality to comment at
282 classroom teaching with as well as like it is able to just go no
283 if they.

284 J: Yeah,

285 N: but that's something we can play with that there's
286 anything.
287 Is just a little bit.
288 It's fine. I can move.

289 S: Yeah

290 N: Everything well found [this claim =
291 J: [uhm
292 N: = said. Look, this is too much (.) say something (.) please.
293 I didn't know you can do that later.

294 S: Umm.
295 Yeah, it's just a content warning.

296 J: It's (.) it's all water. Blood.

297 N: Yeah. No, I've had some pretty
298 choices on that.
299 Working well and but the only good. No. Uh, my God. What is
300 that? But there are the.

301 J: You don't understand.

302 Then I have you in this party to be fun in is satirizing.

303 N: It's a crazy it's not looking at it.

304 J: Yeah, yeah.

305 S: I think the uhm (.)

306 The course is, well, the development from one work to

307 another.

308 Really sets them up with the apparatus to handle brave new

309 [word =

310 N: Yeah, well, about Callum, change sheet.

311 She's a good gateway and this kind of stuff, or even about

312 just takes it to a whole new level

313 S: uhm

314 J: OK, inattentiveness
((Transition Relevance Place, TRP, here))

315 S: Umm.

((Turn Construction Units, TCU and TRPs can be found in Appendix 04 for continuation of the conversation)).

-end of appendix 03-

APPENDIX 04

English Department Collaborative Session (Inclusion Strategies to address Inattentive Student Behaviour during an Online Learning in BINUS SCHOOL Simprug)

Transcription re 13 April 2022 13:30h – 14:10h English Department Meeting

Letter Used to Represent Participant:

JM – [REDACTED] (Subjects Taught: English A, Theory of Knowledge and Psychology)

SG – [REDACTED] (Subjects Taught: English A, English B, Theory of Knowledge)

NY – [REDACTED] (Subjects Taught: English A, Theory of Knowledge)

All teachers above are westerners (i.e., from Canada, UK and Australia)

NB: The conversation provided the perspectives of three teachers as regards to their inclusion strategic practices to address students who are inattentive (a spectrum of ADHD) which were not found in the policy. For example, in the use of diary as an inclusion strategy for inattentiveness, one problem that came out was its superficial use by teachers. The group suggested a whole school approach as a solution. Another example is use of a platform for parent communication which is only in policy but posting has been a challenge. Finally, praising and prompt with positive feedback seemed to be a challenge as it may not work if there is no real contribution by the student.

Time: 13.44.20h – 13.44.27h (6min and 56 second conversation on Inclusion Strategies in dealing with inattentive behaviour of students)

316 J: OK. Inattentive.

317 Good.

318 Like get the help.

319 N: Hey this is me.

320 To come up with something's theories and must (.) must

321 S: Yeah.

322 Supposedly you did really badly in school, right?

323 N: Yeah

324 But by what next impure tell you?

325 Clearly he wasn't terrible.

326 Just wasn't nurtured.

327 S: (H) um (.) fostered (0.7)
 ((Transition Relevance Place, TRP, here))

328 N: We don't have that ((referring to the check diaries))

329 J: No, we used to.

330 N: No, we

331: J: we used (.)

332 we had the daily planner. All students have the book, but

333 I never use
 ((J was honest enough to refer to resources such as student planners but were not used))

334 N: but we need to reintroduce that. We need to
 ((N believes that planners are useful in addressing inattentiveness))

335 <make sure that people use it/>

336 It's very useful I think

337 S: How do (.)

338 you make sure that people use it, though?
 ((S inquires on how to make teachers use a resource which may address inattentiveness))

339 J: Stop. You can [start=

340 N: [with the teachers

341 J: = well

342 N: this is something teachers

343 J: also we checked before back to the [home =

344 S: [and yeah (.) yeah

345 The one you

346 J: =room ((referring to homeroom)) with the type we used to classroom teacher

347 You would do.

348 Yeah. So there's

349 N: the homeroom teacher who checked it. That's what

350 S: yeah, that's what I was (.) most of my responsibility. Other

351 than like picking up people's glasses from, they'll delivered

352 by their own. Whatever. But what it always, eventually comes back

353 down to is the kids who can't be honest right in their agendas

354 Don't do it properly. But I stamp it anyway because they
 ((Concern of S of mere compliance than making planners useful))

355 gotta get it out the door because they're about to get

356 picked up.

357 N: Yeah.

358 S: so (.) there is a lot of slippage (.) that happens
 ((compliance brought about by constraint in time))

359 with that (.)

360 J: uhm

361 N: so like this to get it. And it needs to be a whole

362 school routine
 ((Solution offered by N is whole school approach))

363 S: yeah
 ((Transition Relevance Place, TRP, here))

364 N: not just like.

365 whole school routine not just MYP directive or PYP

366 don't manage it and then it just gets

367 left behind.

368 Needs to be host thing and I come out applicant like

369 S: there could be. I

370 mean in theory you could have a (.) uhm (.) a (.)
371 and our website, [all the students access =
372 J: [there could be
373 S: = and we just upload it to that
374 I'm
375 N: Right.
376 J: and it's probably, I mean it, it ended up
377 N: it doesn't supply.
378 I think [that =
379 S: [Umm
380 N: = will be good.
381 If you don't get printed version, get something they can
382 use and pay attention.
383 And ManageBac ((this is a software programme)) I think
384 It's just that I'm on. We were using. It just doesn't fit well.
385 C: ((Announcements happening during this time)) ((alert chime sound))
386 Dear teachers
387 Only those students to be dismissed today at 1:50. All
388 [must be self-distanced
389 J: [on ohh one 1:50
390 C: ((still announcing)) please make sure
391 to dismiss your students with the transcript for everyone of
392 them to reach their seat on floor 1 by 1:50 (.) Thank you
393 N: on that this morning.
394 absolutely.

395 Crazy. I don't appreciate them to carrying out the lots of
396 downside.
397 Hundred (.) 200 grams.
398 J: Umm
399 N: because we are fighting to help us going to space
400 [getting to
401 J: [yeah (.) we were watching.
402 But a little tired kind of deep in right at the front and
403 made it.
404 Hmm.
(Transition Relevance Place, TRP, here))
405 N: inattentiveness ::
406 Yes (.) so (.) check it out
407 Continue, I would say, say yeah, ManageBac.
408 You know reason is it's not great, it's.
409 It's been updated on what so the system actually very good now.
410 J: umm
411 N: uuuhm ::Teams (referring to Microsoft Teams)) is really
412 really
413 It's not (.)
414 J: maybe not as a (.)
415 N: it's (.) it's (.) actually
416 think it's like,
417 S: yeah, especially in collaboration (.) really
418 N: Alright.
419 Uh, something like a fully institutional tool (.) ManageBac is so

420 much better. Even Google trash.

421 like compared to ManageBac

422 Umm (.) working with parents, you need parent to work here.
 ((working with parents))

423 J: hmm

424 N: better (.) keep post

425 yeah.
 ((Transition Relevance Place, TRP, here))

426 resource from step by step instructions easily OK said.

427 we do that (.)

428 J: Nice (.) really

429 N: facing front feedback.

430 J: I do (.) I do that a lot (.) but try [to

431 N: [Yeah, I don't understand

432 feedback in the classroom (.) Like, if (.) if someone's given an answer.
 ((N provides a solution to inattentiveness by providing feedback))

433 and it's not (.) It's they have to go

434 S: No (.) Yeah (.) for sure

435 N: So you (.) you praise that

436 S: but the point is to establish that you can even work with

437 anything as longer as, as long as there's a carefully

438 considered (.) contribution.

439 N: because even incorrect answer is still takes [off (.) one option =

440 S: [Yeah

441 N: = building those. It's great response.

442 Antarctica pleaded (.) that's my problem [great =
 ((concern of N is providing praise for the sake of it))

443 J: [yeah (.) yeah(.) me too
444 N: = on top of it (.) but formatives in the classroom like
445 anecdotal feedback face to face feedback.
446 fine with that/
447 J: yeah (.) yeah(.) the same. I think we're just overwhelmed
448 with (.) really (.) insane (.)
449 OK, I think that's the final (.) I think I can actually stop the recording
now
(Transition Relevance Place,TRP, here))
-end of Appendix 04-

APPENDIX 5
(consent)

IB World School

7 July 2022

Request for Consent on Use of Data

Dear Messrs. _____,

I am Mr. Erdolfo L. Lardizabal, a graduate student of The University of the Philippines Faculty of Education (student no. 81662-2013). I am writing to request for your consent for me to make use of your conversation transcript (dated 13 April 2022 at 6:27 UTC or 13:27 WIB during your English Department discussion about inclusive education in BINUS SCHOOL Simprug, Jakarta, Indonesia) which data (among others) will be analyzed for my thesis "Perspectives and Practices of Inclusivity in Basic Education: An Ethnomethodological Study of an International Baccalaureate School in Indonesia."

My study is focused on the following research questions:

1. What teaching practices in the school aims to foster inclusivity? and
2. What is the perspective of the school on inclusivity that defines those practices?

I shall be highly grateful for your consent on this request.

Best Regards

Erdolfo Lardizabal

Consent is given:

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Noted by:

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APPENDIX 6

(Inclusion Policy, page 1; PDP on School's Perspective, Page 1)

IB World
School

Ready.
Respectful.
Resilient.

School Inclusion Policy

First Published: July 2006
Reviewed: June 2021

Rationale

BINUS SCHOOL Simprug offers the IB Primary Years Programme, Middle Years Programme, and Diploma Programme.

We believe that we have a responsibility for maximizing the learning outcomes and well-being of all students by providing access to an inclusive high-quality education.

We also believe in learner variability and that all students can learn and understand, but they will do so in different ways, at different rates, and from different starting points.

Through this policy document, the school seeks to ensure that all students have access to the full curriculum and extra-curricular opportunities. As such, all students are integrated into mainstream classes and groups. Students who require modified Learning Support Requirements (LSR) are given opportunities which cater to their needs but do not unfairly advantage or disadvantage them over other students.

Background

BINUS SCHOOL Simprug's vision is fostering and empowering society in building and serving the nation, through nurturing exemplary character, advocating innovative learning and championing compassionate leadership.

Part 2: Programme development

The self-study questionnaire—Part 2: Programme development

Part 2 of the self-study questionnaire asks the school to evidence an aspect of the programme that the school has developed during the period under review. The school shares the planning, implementation, analysis and reflection on the programme development efforts undertaken.

Use of this template is not required but is encouraged. Schools may modify this template or develop their own templates, including the aspects of the process, detailed in the *Guide to programme evaluation*.

Focus of programme development				
What question does the school want to answer? What challenge is the school facing? What goal does the school want to achieve?				
Rationale				
Briefly summarize the reasons the school selected this focus for programme development.				
	Planning		Reflection	
	Guiding questions and prompts	School response	Guiding questions and prompts	School response
		Completed at the start of the programme development planning		Completed at the conclusion of the programme development activities
IB practices	<i>Identify one or two practices to answer each question. Select practices from at least two categories of the PSP framework.</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> What practice or practices need to be in place for this development to be successful? What practice or practices identify the 	C1 (Culture Category). Practice 0301-02. (Who?) The school (How?) implements, communicates and regularly reviews an inclusion policy that create cultures (Why?) to support ALL students to reach their potential!	Indicate if there were any changes to the practices selected and explain why different practices were selected.	We have a new school vision and mission statement which relates to supporting all students to reach their potential. For example, part of our BINUS Misison statement is : Positioning EVERY Binusian at the heart of what we do (Mr. Peter, our Principal's speech last 4 February 2022) This (positioning every Binusian at the heart of what we do) entails:

Self-study questionnaire for use during programme evaluation

Definition of Terms

Online Learning – “Online learning” refers to instructional environments supported by the Internet. Online learning comprises a wide variety of programs that use the Internet within and beyond school walls to provide access to instructional materials as well as facilitate interaction among teachers and students (Graham et. al, 2005).

Inclusion – Inclusion is an ongoing process that aims to increase access and engagement in learning for all students by identifying and removing barriers. This can only be successfully achieved in a culture of collaboration, mutual respect, support, and problem solving. Inclusion is the learner profile in action, an outcome of dynamic learning communities (IBO, 2015)

International Schools – Elite private national schools within the home country, with most students from the home country, which promote an international perspective and student exchanges abroad (Bunnell, 2014: 20-23)

Sense-making knowledge – the action or process of making sense of or giving meaning to something, especially new developments, and experiences (Hornby, 1995)

-nothing follows-